

REINCARNATE

D5.5 – Standardization Plan

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D5.5 – Standardization Plan

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Abstract

The Standardization Plan provides an overview of the current and future standardization activities based on the needs of the REINCARNATE project consortium in the fields of construction and demolition waste to be undertaken during and after the end of the project.

This Plan is drafted by Austrian Standards International (ASI) in collaboration with TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN (TUB), MOSTOSTAL WARSZAWA SA (MOS), AUSTRALO INTERINNOV MARKETING LAB SL (AUS), VIAS Y CONSTRUCCIONES SA (VIAS), CEMEX, ERASMUS UNIVERSITEIT ROTTERDAM (EUR) and RAGN-SELLS AB (RAS).

It provides an overview of the relevant standards identified during the investigation of the standardization landscape and summarizes the priority topics to be addressed within the future standardization activities. It covers topics of wide importance for all spheres of circular economy, Building Information Modelling (BIM), waste management, sustainability in construction and demolition waste (CDW), avoiding CDW in the first place, and being able to reuse CDW in high product quality. Following a Plan-Do-Check-Act methodology, the standardization plan contains focus areas of strategic participation in standardization and a description of actions on how and which standards are implemented in the project.

Keywords

Standards, Standardization Plan, European Standards, International Standards, Horizon Europe

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CDW	Construction and Demolition Waste
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
EN	European Standard
ETSI	European Telecommunication Standards Institute
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Standardization Organisation
NSB	National Standardization Body
NWIP	New Work Item Proposal
SB	Standardization Body
SBO	Standardization Body Organization
SME	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
WI	Work Item

Reincarnate project

The average lifespan of a building is 39 years — in Europe, it is only 25-30 years — and the main reason for demolition is obsolescence. Therefore, there is a large amount of construction and demolition waste (CDW) — representing approximately 25-30% of all waste in Europe —, in addition to that generated in current construction works.

The recycling rate for CDW is relatively high (above 75%). This activity generated \$126.89 billion in 2019 — Europe contributed the largest share, almost two-fifths of the total global market — and is projected to reach \$149.19 billion by 2027. Unfortunately, many of the most valuable materials in CDW cannot be meaningfully separated and end up in landfills.

This helps to get an idea of the efficiency potential for climate neutrality that exists in construction.

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

As a result of these actions, Reincarnate will significantly advance circular economy practices within the European construction industry.

First, it will create a Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) platform and a set of innovations to use it. These solutions will draw upon emerging digital technologies, such as digital twin representation, artificial intelligence, and robotic automation.

3 empirically proven social science insights will allow fostering widespread adoption of reused high-quality construction products and materials, and business eco-system development frameworks to combine actors within sustainable value chains. All innovations will be demonstrated on eleven selected real-world projects and value chains. Furthermore, business process guidelines and an e-learning platform will be developed to drive the dissemination and exploitation of the Reincarnate results.

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1. Introduction

Reincarnate is a funded Horizon Europe project with the aim to revolutionise the construction industry by developing the technical and social means to establish a reincarnation practice within the building sector. 16 organizations, including SMEs, large industries, RTOs and higher education establishments, and non-profits from 6 EU member states, plus Serbia and Hong Kong, are working on:

- Maximize the cumulative virtues of a building, a building product, or a building material during its life.
- Establish a transparent track record of these virtues.
- Use this track record to ensure that a building, building product, or building material can be reused at a high quality in an afterlife.

The project duration extends from June 2022 to May 2026.

1.1. Deliverable Context

1.1.1. Objective of WP 5

This deliverable is the first out of six within the WP 5. Work Package 5 is focused on demonstrating how construction waste can be reduced, both on the level of single buildings, as well as across regional markets. The WP will also provide business process models and standards to allow for the widespread implementation of the REINCARNATE concepts.

1.1.2. Objective of Task 5.4

The objectives of the task 5.4 are

1. Identify and provide an overview of the formal and non-formal construction standards (existing and under development), applicable for sustainable construction and demolition waste.
2. Evaluate the available standards against the needs of the project partners.
3. Elaborate a standardization plan reflecting the partners' needs and update the plan regularly within the duration of the project.

1.1.3. Deliverable Interdependency

The standardization plan developed in Task 5.4 will ensure that the project activities are conducted in line with national, European and international standardization and address the relevant stakeholders. In addition, D5.5 will provide the backbone for the deliverable D5.6, which will be the final Standardization report.

Considering the Reincarnate project vertically, the standardization plan, developed in WP5, will serve as a cornerstone for the work, conducted within the

- WP 1 – REINCARNATE CP-IM
- WP 2 – Solutions for waste reduction and life-time extension
- WP 3 – Solutions for adaptive reuse and recycling
- WP 4 – Social Economic and Market Innovations
- WP 5 – Demonstration and Standardization

Trust into and acceptance of any proposed sustainable construction solution is directly related to its compliance to standards, which guarantees the reliability and interoperability of such a solution.

1.1.4. Purpose of Deliverable 5.5

The purpose of the D5.5 Standardization Plan is to address the objective of the WP5 and elaborate and implement a standardization plan, based on the relevant standards (existing or under development), and provide it to the other WPs for further exploitation. This will ensure that project results are aligned with current regulations and on-going standardisation activities.

The Standardization Plan outlines the initial standardization roadmap in the area of circular and sustainable construction based on the investigation of the standardization landscape, the standardization actions identified using an online survey, and on the standardization needs of Reincarnate consortium partners.

The Standardization Plan (D5.5) and final Standardization Report (D5.6) are part of the Milestone 9, due in Month 48 (May 26).

The standards listed in the first version of this deliverable will be updated. It includes the actions for the focus areas of strategic participation in standardization and a description of how and which standards are implemented in the project.

The present version is the result of two feedback cycles having requested Reincarnate consortium partners to provide their contributions.

D5.5 - Standardization Plan will be updated regularly within the duration of the project and will be transformed to D5.6 – Standardization Report by the end of the project.

1.2 Standardization in a nutshell

In ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004, 1.1 standardization is defined as an activity of establishing, with regard to actual or potential problems, provisions for common and repeated use, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context. Important benefits of standardization are improvement of the suitability of products, processes and services for their intended purposes, prevention of barriers to trade and facilitation of technological cooperation. Standardization supports the social and economic development by ensuring safety, quality and competitiveness of products, services and processes on various levels (e.g. performance, composition, interoperability, applicability and many more). This in turn supports economic activity of businesses of all sizes and allows them access markets all over the world.

Standardization is governed by the principles of consensus, openness, inclusiveness transparency, national commitment and coherence as outlined in the Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade of the World Trade Organisation (WTO TBT Agreement) and in Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on European standardisation.

The output of standardization are standardization documents, such as National Standards, European Standards (EN), International standards (ISO), CEN Workshop Agreements, Technical Specifications and Technical Reports. According to ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004, 3.1 a standard is a document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body, that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context. Standards are voluntary in their application and should be based on the consolidated results of science, technology and experience, and aimed at the promotion of optimum community benefits. Standards are initiated and drafted by stakeholders such as industry, incl. SMEs, public authorities, research organisations, societal and environmental stakeholders, consumer organisations, trade unions and conformity assessment bodies.

There are numerous organizations developing standards, ranging from companies, consortia and industry in the private sector, to national, regional and international organizations. The latter three constitute the bulk of the international standardization system, required by the WTO TBT Agreement to follow its principles and requirements for standards development. There are also NGOs with specific socio-economic or environmental goals that develop and publish standards.

National Standardization Bodies (NSB) are standardization organizations located in each country. They bridge the local communities with groups of relevant stakeholders outside of their country and represent the pillars of the European and International standardization. Being member of European Standardization Organisations NSBs are obliged to implement European Standards as national standards and withdraw any conflicting national standards.

The European standardization activities are conducted within the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation (CENELEC), and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI).

CEN brings together the national standardization bodies of 34 European countries and provides a platform for standardization in various areas, including products, materials, services, and processes. CENELEC ensures standardisation in the electro-technical engineering field, and ETSI produces standards for information and communications technology.

The network of European standardization includes more than 200.000 experts from different countries and from the different stakeholders, i.e. business, industry and commerce, service providers, consumers, environmental and societal organisations, public authorities and regulators, as well as other public and private institutions. The European Standardization Organisations aim to support needs of the market and of different stakeholders, promoting the European Standardization System and leading the implementation of best practice in standardization around the world. They collaborate with key stakeholders' organisations at national, European and international level, support international Standardization and cooperate closely with international Standardization Organisation such as ISO and IEC. Participation in European Standardization follows the national delegation principle, i. e. national members (NSB, NC) host national committees populated with national stakeholders and these national committees contribute to the elaboration of European Standards.

International standardization activities are conducted at three major international Standardization Organisation: International Organization for Standardization (ISO), International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC).

ISO is an independent international organization that includes 165 national standards bodies as its members. International standards, produced by ISO, cover a wide variety of areas and represent consensus of experts from many countries. All CEN members are also members of ISO, with the Vienna Agreement ensuring transparency and exchange of information between them.

Members of IEC are 89 National Committees, represented by delegates from industry, research and government bodies of each country. IEC produces standards covering all aspects of production and use of electrical and electronic devices and systems. All CENELEC members are also members of IEC, their relationship being regulated by the Frankfurt Agreement.

Participation in International Standardization of ISO and IEC follows the national delegation principle, i.e. national members (NSB, NC) host national committees populated with national stakeholders and these national committees contribute to the elaboration of International Standards.

A vast array of normative documents is classed under the generic label of "private standards". Generally, a normative document developed and published by an organization outside of the recognized standards development organizations at national, regional or international level is considered to be a private standard. There is not only a vast range of private standards (and growing in number), but there are also significant differences between the bodies and organizations that develop these standards related to such aspects as governance, development approach, stakeholder engagement, transparency, and consensus.

Identified Technical Committees for Reincarnate are:

- CEN/TC 442 Building Information Modelling (BIM)
- ISO/TC 59/SC 13 Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM)
- ISO/TC 323 Circular Economy
- CEN/TC 350 Sustainability of construction works
- CEN/TC 350/SC 1/ Circular Economy in the Construction Sector

- CEN/TC 183 Waste management

1.1.5. Standardization Procedure Explained

A standardisation procedure usually proceeds in several stages:

1. The subject matter of the standardisation project must be described and, if necessary, comprehensibly delimited from similar subjects that are not to be included.
2. For the elaboration, a committee is convened from all affected technical and interested parties (scientists, producers, users, and political officials). The broadest possible participation of all groups ensures the acceptance and applicability of the standardisation of a subject.
3. First drafts and improvements of a standard are prepared.
4. The draft of a standard is subjected to a public comment and objection procedure, this is to ensure a broad acceptance and applicability of the standard.
5. Objections and suggestions are examined and, if necessary, incorporated into a new version of the standard.

Steps 3 to 5 may be repeated until a satisfactory status is reached and there are no more significant objections.

After final processing, the result of the standardisation procedure is documented as a "standard" in the manner customary for the respective organisation and made available to interested parties and the public.

The flow charts of the standardisation processes correspond to the course of business for standardisation work but may differ depending on the type of standard and the sponsoring organisation. What they all have in common is that standards are developed in a multi-stage procedure in a democratic manner with the involvement of all stakeholders in accordance with the consensus principle. It is not the standardisation organisation that develops standards, but the experts who use it to develop and publish standards. Information on drafting a European Standard is to be found on the [CEN/CENELEC](#) Website. Information about international Standards is to be found on the website of [ISO/IEC](#).

1.3 Methodology

The content for the overview of the standardization landscape is based on a combination of resources, derived from standards databases of the European Committee for Standardization (CEN), European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC), International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) and the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), as well as contributions from the consortium partners (mainly covering non-formal standards). The final standardization landscape covers thus European and international Standardization communities.

Initial literature review on the topic of circular construction sector was conducted by Austrian Standards International. The broad areas of focus were first identified (circular economy, sustainable construction, waste management, building information model), followed by further classification according to the scope of the relevant standardization committees.

The database search was performed using the following keywords:

- Sustainable Construction
- Building Information Model (BIM)
- Waste Management
- Circular Economy

In addition, the relevant technical committees of the European and International Standardization Organization were screened to identify relevant standards that could potentially be missed by the key words.

2. Standardization Landscape

In total, 161 relevant standardization deliverables have been identified so far, comprised of 157 formal standards, one EU funded Horizon 2020 project and one non-formal standard

The identified documents were then grouped for each WP in which they had an impact on the work package's effort.

2.1. Formal Standards

Identified formal standards by standardization bodies with the number of relevant formal standards are listed in Annex 1.

2.2. Non-Formal Standards and Other Relevant Activities

One non-formal standard, developed by the German Association for Water, Wastewater and Waste (DWA) has been identified. Furthermore, another EU-funded Horizon project (ASHVIN) has been identified relevant to this project.

The Non-Formal Standards and Other Relevant Activities are summarized in Annex 2.

2.3. Standards applied to Working Areas of the identified Technical Committees

2.3.1. CEN/TC 442 Building Information Modelling (BIM)

Standardization in the field of structured semantic life-cycle information for the built environment. The committee develops a structured set of standards, specifications and reports which specify methodologies to define, describe, exchange, monitor, record and securely handle asset data, semantics and processes with links to geospatial and other external data.

Following formal and non-formal standards apply to the research in Building Information Modelling:

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Standard	Title	Type of Standard	Status	Consortial Standards, Regulations, Directives, Reference
<u>EN ISO 12006-3:2022</u>	Building construction - Organization of information about construction works - Part 3: Framework for object-oriented information (ISO 12006-3:2022)	E, I	published	
<u>EN ISO 16739-1:2020</u>	Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) for data sharing in the construction and facility management industries - Part 1: Data schema (ISO 16739-1:2018)	E, I	published	
<u>EN ISO 23386:2020</u>	Building information modelling and other digital processes used in construction - Methodology to describe, author and maintain properties in interconnected data dictionaries (ISO 23386:2020)	E, I	published	
<u>EN ISO 23387:2020</u>	Building information modelling (BIM) - Data templates for construction objects used in the life cycle of built assets - Concepts and principles (ISO 23387:2020)	E, I	published	
<u>EN ISO 19650-4</u>	Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) - Information management using building information modelling - Part 4: Information exchange (ISO/FDIS 19650-4:2022)	E, I	published	
<u>prCEN/TR (WI=00442031)</u>	Framework and Implementation of Common Data Environment Solutions, in accordance with EN ISO 19650	E	under drafting	
<u>prEN 17549-1</u>	Building information modelling - Information structure based on EN ISO 16739 1 to exchange data templates and data sheets for construction objects - Part 1: Data templates and configured construction objects	E	under approval	
<u>prEN 17549-2</u>	Building information modelling - Information structure based on EN ISO 16739 1 to exchange data templates and data sheets for construction objects - Part 2: Configurable construction objects and requirements	E	under approval	
<u>prEN ISO 19650-6</u>	ISO 19650-6: Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling -- Information management using building information modelling – Part 6: Health and Safety	E, I	under drafting	
<u>prEN ISO 22014</u>	Library objects for architecture, engineering, and construction	E, I	under drafting	
<u>prEN ISO 23387 rev</u>	Building information modelling (BIM) - Data templates for construction objects used in the life cycle of built assets - Concepts and principles	E, I	under drafting	
<u>EN 17412:2020</u>	Building Information Modelling - Level of Information Need - Part 1: Concepts and principles	E	published	

Table 1 - Identified Standards of CEN/TC

2.3.2. ISO/TC 59/SC 13 Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modeling (BIM)

The scope of ISO/TC 59 is the standardization of terminology, organization of information in building and civil engineering processes, geometric requirements for building, building elements and components including modular coordination, general rules for joints, tolerances and fits; performance requirements of buildings and building elements.

The need for common terminology, rules of information exchanges, measurement techniques and material descriptors increase as globalization and international trade expands. Established standards from ISO/TC 59 have little direct impact upon production, but greater impact on the overall conditions for the industry.

ISO/TC 59/SC 13 is charged by ISO/TC 59 to focus on international standardization of information through the whole life cycle of buildings and infrastructure across the built environment

- to enable interoperability of information.
- to deliver a structured set of standards, specifications, and reports to define, describe, exchange, monitor, record and securely handle information, semantics and processes, with links to geospatial and other related built environment information.
- to enable object-related digital information exchange.

2.3.3. ISO/TC 323 Circular Economy

ISO/TC 323 Technical Committee (“TC”) on Circular Economy (“CE”) has been created in September 2018. This new TC is currently composed of experts from 74 countries (61 participating members and 13 observation members) all around the world. It met for the first time in May 2019, in Paris. More than 120 experts from 47 countries were present to establish the TC. The aim of ISO/TC 323 on Circular Economy is to develop frameworks, guidance’s, supporting tools and requirements for the implementation of activities of all involved organizations to maximize the contribution to Sustainable Development.

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Following formal and non-formal standards apply to the research in ISO/TC 323

Standard	Title	Type of Standard	Status	Consortial Standards, Regulations, Directives, Reference
<u>ISO/CD 59020</u>	Circular economy – Measuring and assessing circularity	I	under development	

Table 2 - Identified Standards of ISO/TC 32

2.3.4. CEN/TC 350 Sustainability of construction works

The committee is responsible for the development of horizontal standardized methods for the assessment of the sustainability aspects of new and existing construction works (buildings and civil engineering works) in the context of the UN Sustainable Development Goals and of the circular economy. The methodological basis will be developed in the context of current needs, European strategies, such as mitigation, adaptation and resilience to climate change, and life cycle thinking. The standards describe coherent methodologies for the assessment of sustainability of construction works covering the assessment of environmental, social and economic performance (aspect and impacts) of buildings and civil engineering works, and the provision of construction product environmental information (EPD).

Following formal and non-formal standards apply to the research in CEN/TC 350:

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Standard	Title	Type of Standard	Status	Consortial Standards, Regulations, Directives, Reference
CEN/TR 15941	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Methodology for selection and use of generic data	E	published	Mandate: M/350
prEN 15941	Sustainability of construction works - Data quality for environmental assessment of products and construction work - Selection and use of data	E	under approval	Mandate: M/350 Amdt
prEN 15978-1	Sustainability of construction works - Methodology for the assessment of performance of buildings - Part 1: Environmental Performance	E	under approval	Mandate: M/350 Amdt
prEN 15978-2	Sustainability of construction works - Methodology for the assessment of buildings - Part 2: Social performance	E	Preliminary	
EN 15978	Sustainability of construction works - Assessment of environmental performance of buildings - Calculation method	E	published	Mandate: M/350
prEN 17680	Sustainability of construction works - Evaluation of the potential for sustainable refurbishment of buildings	E	under approval	
not available (WI=00350038)	Connection between the contributions of CEW to sustainability and achievement of the SDGs	E	Preliminary	
not available (WI=00350040)	Circular economy in the construction sector – Gap analysis, conclusions, and recommendations	E	Preliminary	
not available (WI=00350039)	Circular economy in the construction sector – Framework, principles, and definitions	E	Preliminary	
CEN/TR 16970	Sustainability of construction works - Guidance for the implementation of EN 15804	E	published	Mandate: M/350
CEN/TR 17005	Sustainability of construction works - Additional environmental impact categories and indicators - Background information and possibilities - Evaluation of the possibility of adding environmental impact categories and related indicators and calculation methods for the assessment of the environmental performance of buildings	E	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/350
EN 15643	Sustainability of construction works - Framework for assessment of buildings and civil engineering works	E	published	Mandate: M/350 Amdt
EN 15804	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction products	E	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/350, M/350 Amdt
EN 15804:2012+A2:2019/AC:2021	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction products	E	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/350, M/350 Amdt
EN 15942	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Communication format business-to-business	E	published	Mandate: M/350
EN 16309:2014+A1:2014	Sustainability of construction works - Assessment of social performance of buildings - Calculation methodology	E	published	

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EN 16627	Sustainability of construction works - Assessment of economic performance of buildings - Calculation methods	E	published	
EN 17472	Sustainability of construction works - Sustainability assessment of civil engineering works - Calculation methods	E	published	Mandate: M/526
EN ISO 22057	Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works - Data templates for the use of environmental product declarations (EPDs) for construction products in building information modelling (BIM) (ISO 22057:2022)	E, I	published	

Table 3 - Identified Standards CEN/TC 350

2.3.5. CEN/TC 350/SC 1/ Circular Economy in the Construction Sector

Standardization in the field of circular economy in the built environment specifying circular principles and guidelines and requirements to facilitate the transition to a more sustainable circular economy including tools and processes to achieve this; covering design to de-construction and end-of-life scenarios in all stages of current and subsequent life cycles. This applies to new and existing construction works (buildings and civil engineering works), including their products, materials, and components. The Subcommittee deals both with technical issues on circularity, as well as environmental, economic, and social challenges. This work will consider standards of CEN/TC 350 and consider the work of existing committees on subjects that may support the circular economy in the construction sector, such as ISO/TC 323 and CEN-CLC/JTC 10, including initiatives of the European Commission.

Following formal and non-formal standards apply to the research in CEN/TC 350/SC 1: please see table 3.

2.3.6. CEN/TC 183 Waste Management

Standardization in the field waste management including public cleaning, taking into particular account technical and logistical aspects. Drafting of Standards for products and procedures as well as safety requirements for the collection, transport, storage and transfer of solid and liquid waste. The characterization of waste and sludge as well as functional aspects for snow clearing equipment and road service area maintenance equipment is not covered by the scope of CEN/TC 183.

Following formal and non-formal standards apply to the research in CEN/TC 183

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Standard	Title	Type of Standard	Status	Consortial Standards, Regulations, Directives, Reference
EN 14803	Identification and/or determination of the quantity of waste	E	published	

Table 4 - Identified Standards of CEN/TC 183

3. Gap Analysis

Based on the first version of the standardization plan, a gap analysis will be carried out in collaboration with the work packages from 1 to 5 and the respective work package and task leaders. These gaps will be identifiable after the initial findings of the Work Packages. Upcoming versions of Deliverable 5.5 and the final Standard Report (D5.6) will include the final gap analysis.

The gap analysis serves as a basis for making the results of the research projects available to an international audience to create new standards for the market.

This can be done with the participation of experts from REINCARNATE, considering the delegation principle after the end of the project. For this, see point 5.1

4. Standardization Plan

Based on the research on standardization, the standardization plan devised in the project is based on the PDCA (Plan – Do – Check – Act) methodology. This involves pursuing the following activities:

Figure 1 - PDCA Cycle, Source: <https://www.sixsigmablackbelt.de/>

- **Phase Plan:**

Based on the research a decision on standards relevant for the project is carried out.

- **Phase Do:**

The project partners ensure the compatibility and interoperability of their services and technical solutions with the relevant standards.

Partners contribute towards the compliance, application, and development of standards in the areas of relevance to REINCARNATE.

Project partners contribute to activities in Standards Development Organizations (SDOs).

- **Phase Check:**

Partners, especially those involved in WP 1, WP 2, WP 3, WP 4 and WP 5, shall periodically review and align their standardization activities and provide an update for internal and external awareness. The findings will be used to update D5.5 regularly and develop the final Standardization report D5.6.

- **Phase Act:**

If the new subject areas relevant to the project are planned or identified by SDOs (e.g. CEN, CENELEC, ETSI, IEC, ISO, IEEE) the partners have to create a corresponding analysis of the target status and compare it with the current status. Furthermore, the questions of what can be optimized and where lay a further potential of standardization activities must be clarified. If it is determined that the goal has not been reached, the cycle is run through again.

4.1. Standardization Plan per Work Area

The results of Reincarnates research using selected standards by the project's stakeholders will be specifically embedded in the standardization networks during the course of the project. Concrete results are expected in Deliverable 5.6.

5. Standardization Network and Strategic Areas of Participation

The analysis of the ongoing standardization activities in the project and partners interests reveals the following key areas that require an active participation from a project's strategic point of view.

Those partners participating in the following standardization areas are committed to report latest and important developments to the project and feed findings from the project back to standardization. Such two-way interaction between Reincarnate and standardization communities contributes to an optimal alignment of the project activities and outcomes with standards (published and under development).

In case, no other partner participates in a standardization body listed below, ASI as member of CEN, ISO, ETSI and having contacts with CENELEC and IEC will be used as communication channel.

- CEN/TC 442 Building Information Modelling (BIM)
- ISO/TC 59/SC 13 Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM)
- ISO/TC 323 Circular Economy
- CEN/TC 350 Sustainability of construction works
- CEN/TC 350/SC 1/ Circular Economy in the Construction Sector
- CEN/TC 183 Waste Management

5.1. Best Practice Approach for Active Participation in Standardization

The best approach to represent the whole REINCARNATE project in European and international standardisation bodies would be to appoint an expert as Liaison Officer.

On the one hand, this decision has to be made within the consortium and a request has to be submitted to the selected committees. The liaison officer officially represents the views of the research project and not those of his or her own organisation. Accordingly, constant feedback is desired in order to generate constructive synergies.

Another option is to be sent to selected international bodies as a delegated expert from the national standardisation body, although this is disadvantageous for the project, as

the interests of the respective national standardisation body and not those of the project are represented via this access.

Further information on liaisons is available here for [ISO/IEC](#) and for [CEN/CENELEC](#).

6. Conclusion

Throughout the REINCARNATE project, the present deliverable (D5.5) supports partners in integrating standardization related activities in their work packages. As a result, it contributes to enhancing ongoing standardisation efforts and increasing the understanding of how research and development may contribute to standardisation.

As underlined by the number of existing technical bodies, standardisation deliverables focusing on or in connection with sustainability in construction, standardisation plays an essential role in topic areas related to the REINCARNATE project.

The elaborated lists of formal and non-formal standardisation deliverables indicated in Annex I and Annex II are a first step towards novel standards relevant to the REINCARNATE project. The lists are subject to change and are planned to be used as a significant basis for assessing a potential contribution to standardisation activities throughout the project. Furthermore, the lists will be adapted based on the research developments throughout the project timeline and partnerships with existing Technical Committees strengthened.

Research and technical results in REINCARNATE will be collaboratively used for drafting a solid standardization report and plan. The aim of this plan will be described in the deliverable 5.6.

Annex 1:

Standard	Title	Type of Standard	Summary or Scope	Status	Consortial Standards, Regulations, Directives, Reference	Standardization Body & Technical Committees & Working Groups (CEN/CENELEC; ISO/IEC, ETSI; IEEE etc)
	<i>Explanation:</i>			<i>Preliminary</i>		
	<i>ÖNORM B XXXX</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>National Standard</i>	<i>published</i>		
	<i>EN XXXXXX-XX</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>European Standard</i>	<i>under development</i>	<i>EG/XXX-XXXX-XXX</i>	<i>ISO/TC XXX/SC XX/WG XX</i>
	<i>ISO XXXXXX-XX</i>	<i>I</i>	<i>International Standard</i>	<i>under approval</i>		
	<i>XXXX-XXXX</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>Other type of document and/or resource, e.g. H2020 projects</i>	<i>under Enquiry</i>		
EN 17213:2020 (WI=00033503)	Windows and doors - Environmental Product Declarations - Product category rules for windows and pedestrian doorsets	E	This document provides product category rules (PCR) for Type III environmental declarations for windows and pedestrian doorsets as defined in EN 14351-1 and EN 14351-2. Windows and pedestrian doorsets additionally providing fire resistance and/or smoke control characteristics according to EN 16034 are also covered by this document. NOTE 1 Windows that incorporate shutters and/or shutter boxes and/or blinds are in scope of this PCR. For any connected electrical devices (e.g. motors, sensors) -see 6.3.4.2. This document complements the core rules for the product category of construction products as defined in the European standard EN 15804:2012+A1:2013. The document is to be used in conjunction with EN 15804:2012+A1:2013, not replace it. NOTE 2 The assessment of social and economic performances at product level is not covered by this document. The core PCR: - defines the parameters to be declared and the way in which they are collated and reported; - describes which stages of a product's life cycle are considered in the EPD and which processes are to be included in the life cycle stages; - defines rules for the development of scenarios; - includes the rules for calculating the Life Cycle Inventory and the Life Cycle Impact Assessment underlying the EPD, including the specification of the data quality to be applied; - includes the rules for reporting the predetermined, environmental and health information that is not covered by Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for the product,	published		CEN/TC 033

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			construction process(es) and construction service(s), as relevant; - defines the conditions under which construction products can be compared based on the information provided by EPD. For the EPD of construction services the same rules and requirements apply as for the EPD of construction products.			
EN 17610:2022 (WI=00033542)	Building hardware - Environmental product declarations - Product category rules complementary to EN 15804 for building hardware	E	This document provides product category rules (PCR) for Type III environmental declarations for: - Building hardware products for opening and closing doors, gates, windows and shutters: -- Lever handles and knob furniture (EN 1906); -- Single-axis hinges (EN 1935); -- Hardware for windows and door height windows (EN 13126 (all parts)); -- Fittings for shutters (e.g. EN 14648); -- Controlled door closing devices, electrically powered hold-open devices for swing doors and door coordinator devices (EN 1154, EN 1155, EN 1158); -- Hardware for sliding doors, folding doors and roll fronts (EN 1527, EN 15706); -- Glass door gear; - Building hardware products for locking and unlocking doors, gates, windows and shutters: -- Mechanically operated locks and locking plates, multipoint locks, latches and locking plates (EN 12209, EN 15685); -- Cylinders for locks (EN 1303); -- Padlocks and padlock fittings (EN 12320); -- Mechanically operated push-button locksets (BS 8607); -- Emergency exit devices operated by a lever handle or push pad, for use on escape routes and panic exit devices operated by a horizontal bar, for use on escape routes (EN 179, EN 1125); - Electromechanical building hardware products: -- Mechatronic cylinders (EN 15684); -- Mechatronic padlocks (EN 16864); -- Mechatronic door furniture (EN 16867); -- Electromechanically operated locks and striking plates (EN 14846); -- Electrically controlled exit systems for use on escape routes (EN 13637). This document complements the core rules for the product category of construction products as defined in the European standard EN 15804:2012+A2:2019. NOTE The assessment of social and economic performances at product level is not covered by this document. The core PCR: - defines the parameters to be declared and the way in which they are collated and reported; - describes which stages of a product's life cycle are considered in the EPD and which processes are to be included in the life cycle stages; - defines rules for the development of scenarios; - includes the rules for calculating the Life Cycle Inventory and the Life Cycle Impact Assessment underlying the EPD, including the specification of the data quality to be applied; - includes the rules for reporting the predetermined, environmental and health information that is not covered by Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for the product, construction process(es) and construction service(s), as relevant; - defines	published		CEN/TC 033

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			the conditions under which construction products can be compared based on the information provided by EPD. For the EPD of construction services the same rules and requirements apply as for the EPD of construction products.			
prEN 197-6	Cement - Part 6: Cement with recycled building materials	E	This document deals with cement with recycled building materials whose intended use is the preparation of concrete, mortar, grout, etc.	under approval		CEN/TC 051
EN 16908:2017+A1:2022 (WI=00051154)	Cement and building lime - Environmental product declarations - Product category rules complementary to EN 15804	E	The general scope of the core product category rules (PCR) is given in EN 15804:2012+A2:2019, Clause 1. This PCR is primarily intended for the creation of cradle-to-gate EPDs of cement and building lime. In other respects, the scope is as in EN 15804:2012+A2:2019.	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/355	CEN/TC 051
EN 17160:2019 (WI=00067119)	Product category rules for ceramic tiles	E	This document defines Product Category Rules (PCR) providing guidelines and rules for developing a type III environmental declaration (EPD) for ceramic tiles produced by extrusion and dry-pressing techniques, mainly used for internal and/or external floorings and walls coverings and façade cladding. These PCR specify the calculation rules in accordance with EN 15804:2012+A1:2013 for the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of ceramic tiles for developing an EPD, as well as the requirements on the background of the LCA. These PCR: - define the parameters to be declared and the way in which they are collated and reported; - describe which stages of ceramic tiles's life cycle are considered in the EPD and which processes are to be included in the life cycle stages; - defines rule for the development of scenarios; - include the rules for calculating the Life Cycle Inventory and the Life Cycle Impact Assessment underlying the EPD, including the specification of the data quality to be applied; - include the rules for reporting predetermined, environmental and health information, that is not covered by LCA for a ceramic tile, construction process and construction service where necessary; - define the conditions under which ceramic tiles can be compared based on the information provided by EPD. The EPD developed using these PCR will contain data from the product stages (A1 to A3). Optionally, the manufacturer can include all modules of the product's life cycle stages (construction process, use, and end of life) (A4 to C4), using the scenarios described in 7.3 when primary data are not available. The results of these stages shall be shown individually (without being added together). Therefore, these PCR cover: - EPD cradle-to-gate (only the product stage is considered); - EPD cradle-to-grave (the whole life cycle of ceramic tiles is considered). In these type of EPD module D may be included. After verification an EPD is valid for a 5 year	published		CEN/TC 067

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			period from the date of issue, after which it shall be reviewed and verified.			
EN 16783:2017 (WI=00088334)	Thermal insulation products - Product category rules (PCR) for factory made and in-situ formed products for preparing environmental product declarations	E	This European Standard provides the product category rules (PCR) for Type III environmental declarations (as in EN 15804) for factory made and in situ thermal insulation products. Complementary to EN 15804, the PCR described in this European Standard: - specify the declared unit to be used; - define the system boundaries for thermal insulation products; - specify/describe the default scenarios and rules for defining scenarios for certain life cycle information modules. These PCR are intended to be used for cradle to gate, cradle to gate with options or cradle to grave assessment, provided the intention is properly stated in the system boundary description.	published		CEN/TC 088
prEN 16783 (WI=00088485)	Thermal insulation products - Product category rules (PCR) for factory made and in-situ formed products for preparing environmental product declarations	E	This document provides the product category rules (PCR) for Type III environmental declarations (as in EN 15804:2012+A2:2019+AC:2021) for factory made and in situ thermal insulation products. Complementary to EN 15804:2012+A2:2019+AC:2021, the PCR described in this document: - specify the declared unit to be used; - define the system boundaries for thermal insulation products; - specify/describe the default scenarios and rules for defining scenarios for certain life cycle information modules. These PCR are intended to be used for cradle to gate, cradle to gate with options or cradle to grave assessment, provided the intention is properly stated in the system boundary description.	under Enquiry		CEN/TC 088
EN 206	Concrete - Specification, performance, production and conformity	E	(1) This European Standard applies to concrete for structures cast in situ, precast structures, and structural precast products for buildings and civil engineering structures. (2) The concrete under this European Standard can be: - normal-weight, heavy-weight and light-weight; - mixed on site, ready-mixed or produced in a plant for precast concrete products; - compacted or self-compacting to retain no appreciable amount of entrapped air other than entrained air. (3) This standard specifies requirements for: - the constituents of concrete; - the properties of fresh and hardened concrete and their verification; - the limitations for concrete composition; - the specification of concrete; - the delivery of fresh concrete; - the production control procedures; - the conformity criteria and evaluation of conformity. (4) Other European Standards for specific products e.g. precast products or for processes within the field of the scope of this standard may require or permit deviations. (5) Additional or different requirements may be given for specific applications in other European Standards, for example: - concrete to be used in roads and other trafficked areas (e.g. concrete pavements according to EN 13877-1); - special technologies (e.g. sprayed concrete according to EN 14487). (6) Supplementing requirements or	published		CEN/TC 104

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			different testing procedures may be specified for specific types of concrete and applications, for example: - concrete for massive structures (e.g. dams); - dry mixed concrete; - concrete with a Dmax of 4 mm or less (mortar); - self-compacting concretes (SCC) containing lightweight or heavy-weight aggregates or fibres; - concrete with open structure (e.g. pervious concrete for drainage). (7) This standard does not apply to: - aerated concrete; - foamed concrete; - concrete with density less than 800 kg/m ³ ; - refractory concrete. (8) This standard does not cover health and safety requirements for the protection of workers during production and delivery of concrete.			
prEN 17662 (WI=00135029)	Execution of steel structures and aluminium structures - Environmental Product Declarations - Product category rules complementary to EN 15804 for Steel, Iron and Aluminium structural products for use in construction works	E	This European standard provides product category rules (c-PCR), that are complementary to EN 15804, for Type III environmental declarations for steel components and aluminium components fabricated from steel or aluminium constituent products to be used for structural purposes in buildings and civil engineering works where their characteristic affects the mechanical resistance and stability of these construction works or parts thereof, where there does not exist a more specific specification for the product. This standard also provides guidance for other metal construction products where a specific PCR as EN standard does not exist.	under approval		CEN/TC 135
EN 12620	Aggregates for concrete	E	This European Standard specifies the properties of aggregates and filler aggregates obtained by processing natural, manufactured or recycled materials and mixtures of these aggregates for use in concrete. It covers aggregates having an oven dried particle density greater than 2,00 Mg/m ³ (2 000 kg/m ³) for all concrete, including concrete in conformity with EN 206-1 and concrete used in roads and other pavements and for use in precast concrete products. It also covers recycled aggregate with densities between 1,50 Mg/m ³ (1 500 kg/m ³) and 2,00 Mg/m ³ (2 000 kg/m ³) with appropriate caveats and recycled fine aggregate (4 mm) with appropriate caveats." It also specifies that a quality control system is in place for use in factory production control and it provides for the evaluation of conformity of the products to this European Standard. This standard does not cover filler aggregates to be used as a constituent in cement or as other than inert filler aggregates for concrete. NOTE 1 Aggregates used in construction should comply with all the requirements of this European Standard. As well as familiar and traditional natural and manufactured aggregates Mandate M/125 "Aggregates" included recycled aggregates and some materials from new or unfamiliar sources. Recycled aggregates are included in the standards and new test methods for them are at an advanced	published	Citation: C 259 (2014-08-08) for Directive 305/2011, C 321 (2008-12-16) for Directive 89/106/EEC ; Mandate: M/125	CEN/TC 154

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			stage of preparation. For unfamiliar materials from secondary sources, however, the work on standardisation has only started recently and more time is needed to define clearly the origins and characteristics of these materials. In the meantime such unfamiliar materials when placed on the market as aggregates must comply fully with this standard and national regulations for dangerous substances (see Annex ZA of the standard) depending upon their intended use. Additional characteristics and requirements may be specified on a case by case basis depending upon experience of use of the product, and defined in specific co			
prEN 16903 (WI=00155958)	Plastics piping systems - Environmental product declarations - Product Category Rules complementary to EN 15804, for buried plastics piping systems	E	This document provides product category rules (PCR) for Type III environmental product declarations, as described in EN ISO 14025 and EN 15942, for "buried plastics piping systems" intended for buried pressure and non-pressure applications outside building structure. This PCR covers the entire life cycle from cradle to grave for buried plastics piping systems conveying fluids (sewer, water or gas), according to EN 12007, EN 805 or EN 476. NOTE The PCR will be applied to systems composed of products covered by the list of product standards provided in Annex D. This document specifies the rules for the product category of construction products as defined in and is intended to be used in conjunction with EN 15804. As in EN 15804:2012+A2:2019, in addition to the common parts of EN 15804, this document for buried plastics piping systems defines: - the functional unit; - the system boundaries; - the elements of installation; - the transport scenarios for both the raw material and the complete system; - the trench conditions; - reference service life (RSL); - end of life scenarios.	under approval		CEN/TC 155
prEN 16904 (WI=00155957)	Plastics piping systems - Environmental product declarations - Product Category rules complementary to EN 15804, for plastic piping systems inside buildings	E	This document provides product category rules (PCR) for Type III environmental product declarations, as described in EN ISO 14025 and EN 15942, for "buried plastics piping systems" intended for buried pressure and non-pressure applications outside building structure. This PCR covers the entire life cycle from cradle to grave for buried plastics piping systems conveying fluids (sewer, water or gas), according to EN 12007, EN 805 or EN 476. NOTE The PCR will be applied to systems composed of products covered by the list of product standards provided in Annex D. This document specifies the rules for the product category of construction products as defined in and is intended to be used in conjunction with EN 15804. As in EN 15804:2012+A2:2019, in addition to the common parts of EN 15804, this document for buried plastics piping systems defines: - the functional unit; - the system boundaries; - the elements of installation; - the transport scenarios for both the raw material and the complete system; - the trench conditions; - reference service life (RSL); - end of life scenarios.	under approval		CEN/TC 155

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<p><u>EN 16485:2014</u> <u>(WI=00175150)</u></p>	<p>Round and sawn timber - Environmental Product Declarations - Product category rules for wood and wood-based products for use in construction</p>	<p>E</p>	<p>This European Standard provides general Product Category Rules (PCR) for Type III environmental declarations for wood and wood-based products for use in construction and related construction and in-service processes. This European Standard complements the core rules for the product category of construction products as defined in EN 15804 and is intended to be used in conjunction with EN 15804. NOTE The assessment of social and economic performances at product level is not covered by this standard. The core PCR: — define the parameters to be declared and the way in which they are collated and reported; — describe which stages of a product's life cycle are considered in the EPD and which processes are to be included in the life cycle stages; — define rules for the development of scenarios; — include the rules for calculating the Life Cycle Inventory and the Life Cycle Impact Assessment underlying the EPD, including the specification of the data quality to be applied; — include the rules for reporting predetermined, environmental and health information, that is not covered by LCA for a product, construction process and construction service where necessary; — define the conditions under which construction products can be compared based on the information provided by EPD. For the EPD of construction services, the same rules and requirements apply as for the EPD of construction products. Additionally to the common parts of EN 15804, this European Standard for wood and wood-based products: — defines the system boundaries; — defines the rules for modelling and assessment of material-specific characteristics such as carbon storage and energy content of wood; — defines allocation procedures for multi-output processes along the wood chain; — defines allocation procedures for reuse, recycling and energy recovery; — includes the rules for calculating the Life Cycle Inventory and the Life Cycle Impact Assessment underlying the EPD, including the assessment of carbon and energy content of wood; — provides guidance/specific rules for the determination of the Reference Service Life (RSL). This European Standard is intended to be used for cradle to gate or cradle to grave assessment, provided the intention is properly stated in the system boundary description.</p>	<p>published</p>		<p><u>CEN/TC 175</u></p>
<p><u>EN 14803</u></p>	<p>Identification and/or determination of the quantity of waste</p>	<p>E</p>	<p>This document specifies general requirements and verifications for methods of identification of waste containers and/or determination of the quantity of waste and other reusable materials including: - safety requirements; - interface requirements and performances; - data to be treated and their integrity. This document is applicable to systems for handling containers conforming to the EN 840 series. Although this document does not cover systems for handling containers not</p>	<p>published</p>		<p><u>CEN/TC 183</u></p>

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			conforming to the EN 840 series, users are encouraged to apply the requirements of this document to these systems as far as possible. This document is applicable to systems both for billing and not for billing. This document is applicable to systems both for billing and not for billing.			
EN 16757:2022	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Product Category Rules for concrete and concrete elements	E	This European Standard complements the core rules for the product category of construction products as defined in EN 15804:2012+A1:2013 and is intended to be used in conjunction with that standard. This European Standard applies to concrete and concrete elements for building and civil engineering, excluded autoclaved aerated concrete. This document defines the parameters to be reported, what EPD types (and life cycle stages) to be covered, what rules to be followed in order to generate Life Cycle Inventories (LCI) and conduct Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) and the data quality to be used in the development of EPDs. In addition to the common parts of EN 15804:2012+A1:2013, this European Standard for concrete and concrete elements: - defines the system boundaries; - defines the modelling and assessment of material-specific characteristics; - defines allocation procedures for multi-output processes along the production chain; - defines allocation procedures for reuse and recycling; - includes the rules for calculating the LCI and the LCIA underlying the EPD; - provides guidance/specific rules for the determination of the reference service life (RSL); - gives guidance on the establishment of default scenarios; - gives guidance on default functional units for concrete elements. This document is intended to be used either for cradle to gate, cradle to gate with options or cradle to grave assessment, provided the intentions are properly stated in the system boundary description. Within the construction works context, a cradle to grave declaration delivers a more comprehensive understanding of the environmental impact associated with concrete and concrete elements.	published		CEN/TC 229
CEN/TR 15941	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Methodology for selection and use of generic data	E	This Technical Report supports the development of Environmental Product Declarations (EPD). It assists in using generic data according to the core product category rules (prEN 15804) during the preparation of EPD of construction products, processes and services in a consistent way, and also in the application of generic data in the environmental performance assessment of buildings according to prEN 15978. The requirements for the use of generic data are described in prEN 15804.	published	Mandate: M/350	CEN/TC 350
prEN 15941	Sustainability of construction works - Data quality for environmental	E	This document supports the data quality assessment and selection of data for product-level Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) according to the core product category rules of EN 15804 and for the environmental performance	under approval	Mandate: M/350 Amdt	CEN/TC 350

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	assessment of products and construction work - Selection and use of data		assessment of buildings according to prEN 15978 1 in a consistent way. It can also be used to assess and select data for the environmental assessment of civil engineering works according to EN 17472. It defines data quality requirements with respect to temporal, technological and geographical representativeness for the data used to calculate the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) based indicator results of the EPD and for construction works when applying EPD, life cycle inventory data or other LCA based information, and generates a hierarchy to support the selection of the most appropriate data with regard to data quality. It also addresses the reporting of data quality at product and building level.			
<u>prEN 15978-1</u>	Sustainability of construction works - Methodology for the assessment of performance of buildings - Part 1: Environmental Performance	E	This European Standard specifies the calculation method, based on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and other quantified environmental information, to assess the environmental performance of a building, and gives the means for the reporting and communication of the outcome of the assessment. The standard is applicable to new and existing buildings and refurbishment projects. The standard gives: - the description of the object of assessment; - the system boundary that applies at the building level; - the procedure to be used for the inventory analysis; - the list of indicators and procedures for the calculations of these indicators; - the requirements for presentation of the results in reporting and communication; - and the requirements for the data necessary for the calculation. The approach to the assessment covers all stages of the building life cycle and is based on data obtained from Environmental Product Declarations (EPD), their "information modules" (prEN 15804) and other information necessary and relevant for carrying out the assessment. The assessment includes all building related construction products, processes and services, used over the life cycle of the building. The interpretation and value judgments of the results of the assessment are not within the scope of this European Standard.	under approval	Mandate: M/350 Amdt	<u>CEN/TC 350</u>
<u>prEN 15978-2</u>	Sustainability of construction works - Methodology for the assessment of buildings - Part 2: Social performance	E	This European Standard is one part of a suite of European Standards. The standard provides the specific methods and requirements for the assessment of social performance of a building while taking into account the building's functionality and technical characteristics. This European Standard applies to all types of buildings, both new and existing. In this first version of the standard, the social dimension of sustainability concentrates on the assessment of aspects and impacts for the use stage of a building expressed using the following social performance categories (from EN 15643 3): - accessibility; - adaptability; - health and comfort; - impacts on the neighbourhood; - maintenance; - safety and security. NOTE 1	Preliminary		<u>CEN/TC 350</u>

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			<p>Only impacts and aspects of the above social performance categories are deemed to have an agreed basis for European standardization at this time. Two of the social performance categories included in EN 15643-3 (sourcing of materials and services and stakeholder involvement) are not deemed to be ready for standardization at this time and will be considered for inclusion in future versions of this standard (see informative Annex C). This standard does not set the rules for how building assessment schemes may provide valuation methods. Nor does it prescribe levels, classes or benchmarks of performance. Valuation methods, levels, classes or benchmarks may be prescribed in the requirements for environmental, social and economic performance in the client's brief, building regulations, national standards, national codes of practice, building assessment and certification schemes, etc. NOTE 2 Where National building regulations give minimum requirements and reference to assessment methods on these aspects, the social performance determined by assessment according to this standard can be used to determine the degree to which the building goes beyond the regulatory/legal requirements. The corporate social responsibility (CSR) of organizations is not covered by this standard. The standard gives requirements for: - the description of the object of assessment; - the system boundary that applies at the building level; - the list of indicators and procedures for the application of these indicators; - the presentation of the results in reporting and communication; - the data necessary for the application of the standard, and - verification.</p>			
<u>EN 15978</u>	Sustainability of construction works - Assessment of environmental performance of buildings - Calculation method	E	<p>This European Standard specifies the calculation method, based on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and other quantified environmental information, to assess the environmental performance of a building, and gives the means for the reporting and communication of the outcome of the assessment. The standard is applicable to new and existing buildings and refurbishment projects. The standard gives: - the description of the object of assessment; - the system boundary that applies at the building level; - the procedure to be used for the inventory analysis; - the list of indicators and procedures for the calculations of these indicators; - the requirements for presentation of the results in reporting and communication; - and the requirements for the data necessary for the calculation. The approach to the assessment covers all stages of the building life cycle and is based on data obtained from Environmental Product Declarations (EPD), their "information modules" (prEN 15804) and other information necessary and relevant for carrying out the</p>	published	Mandate: M/350	<u>CEN/TC 350</u>

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			assessment. The assessment includes all building related construction products, processes and services, used over the life cycle of the building. The interpretation and value judgments of the results of the assessment are not within the scope of this European Standard.			
prEN 17680	Sustainability of construction works - Evaluation of the potential for sustainable refurbishment of buildings	E	This document provides a methodology for the evaluation of the potential for sustainable refurbishment of an existing building, as a means of contributing to the circular economy, to support the decision-making process. Sustainable refurbishment aims to close the gap between current performance and current requirements fulfilling authorities' sustainability regulations and contribute to meet sustainability goals which maximizes the environmental, social and economic performance. It also aims to allow the adaptability to fulfil future needs. It can be used for a building or part(s) of a building, as well as a portfolio of buildings. This document gives a methodology for assessing performance characteristics of existing buildings in terms of: 1) Technical aspects 2) Adaptability 3) Usability 4) Social aspects 5) Energy, water and operational impacts 6) Quality of indoor environment (including health aspects) 7) Economic feasibility 8) Climate change resilience 9) Embodied environmental impacts The document describes the work to be done in main applicable categories of a 6 steps process: · Step 0: Establish brief of the object of the assessment · Step 1: Evaluating the building · Step 2: Sustainable deconstruction · Step 3: Sustainable construction process · Step 4: Sustainable commissioning · Step 5: Sustainable in use NOTE In this document the users are people and organisations using the building, including the facility management. In some buildings visitors are also important users and need to be taken into account. This approach is generic for all types of buildings. At present this document does not cover civil engineering work and it does not give benchmarks for the evaluation. Assessment of the impacts of sustainable refurbishment of buildings is covered by calculation methods described in EN 15978, EN 16309 and EN 16627.	under approval		CEN/TC 350
not available (WI=00350038)	Connection between the contributions of CEW to sustainability and achievement of the SDGs	E		Preliminary		CEN/TC 350
-						
CEN/TR 16970	Sustainability of construction works - Guidance for the	E	This Technical Report provides general guidance to the users of EN 15804 and those preparing complementary Product Category Rules (c-PCR's) by: — stating general principles for	published	Mandate: M/350	CEN/TC 350

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	implementation of EN 15804		the use of EN 15804 by CEN Technical Committees for construction products (Product TC's) in order to ensure consistency among the complementary PCR produced by Product TC's; — addressing the questions raised by Product TC's, manufacturers or their sub-contractors who provide LCA studies underlying an Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) and by EPD programme operators who include c-PCR of specific subcategories in their PCR registry.			
<u>CEN/TR 17005</u>	Sustainability of construction works - Additional environmental impact categories and indicators - Background information and possibilities - Evaluation of the possibility of adding environmental impact categories and related indicators and calculation methods for the assessment of the environmental performance of buildings	E	This Technical Report (TR) has been developed by CEN/TC 350/WG 1 and WG 3 to provide a clear and structured view on the relevance, robustness and applicability of a predefined set of additional impact categories and related indicators for the assessment of the environmental performance of construction works, construction products and building materials. The TR describes the evaluation criteria that are used to determine, for these impact categories, the suitability of indicators and calculation method(s) for inclusion in the standards EN 15978 and EN 15804 (or other CEN/TC 350 standards as appropriate) in terms of their: a) relevance to: 1) the environment, 2) construction works, 3) construction products, and 4) EU policy; b) scientific robustness and certainty; and c) applicability of the impact assessment method(s). The additional impact categories examined in the TR are: - human toxicity and ecotoxicity; - particulate matter; - land use; - biodiversity; - water scarcity; and - ionizing radiation. Because EN 15978 and EN 15804 are founded on a life cycle approach, the impact categories, indicators and methods reviewed are predominantly based on their potential suitability for application in LCA. In relation to some of the areas of concern, however, where LCA methods might not be sufficiently robust or developed, some non-LCA based indicators and methods are also considered. Due to the scope of LCA used in the EN 15804 and EN 15978, impacts to users of buildings due to direct exposure to harmful emissions fall outside the scope of this TR. This falls under the scope of CEN/TC 351. Important information related to this aspect found during the development of this TR, is however mentioned in the TR. Uncertainty is an important issue in LCA. General assessment of the uncertainty related to impact assessment models is considered in the evaluation framework of this TR. However, the TR does not lay down a maximum uncertainty level to be considered acceptable in the context of the CEN standards EN 15804 and EN 15978, nor does it provide exact figures on uncertainties. Annex A of the TR provides a description of options that may be considered for incorporating selected impact categories/indicator in the standards EN 15978 and EN 15804. The TR recognizes and takes account of: - the work	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/350	<u>CEN/TC 350</u>

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			done by the European Commission, Joint Research Centre (EC-JRC), in the development of the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) Handbook Recommendations, - other reports and scientific studies into the methods and application of the indicators reviewed, - findings of specific activities connected with this work such as of the CEN/TC 350 Workshop, held in Brussels on 24-25 June 2014.			
<u>EN 15643</u>	Sustainability of construction works - Framework for assessment of buildings and civil engineering works	E	This document provides principles and requirements for the assessment of environmental, social and economic performance of buildings and civil engineering works taking into account their technical characteristics and functionality. NOTE 1 Assessments of environmental, social and economic performance are the three aspects of sustainability assessment of buildings and civil engineering works, or combination thereof, (hereafter referred to as "construction works"). The framework applies to all types of construction works and it is relevant for new construction works over their entire life cycle, and of existing construction works over their remaining service life and end of life stage. The sustainability assessment of construction works covers aspects and impacts of construction works expressed with quantifiable indicators. It includes the assessment of the construction works' influence on the environmental, social and economic aspects and impacts on the local area (area of influence) and of the local infrastructure beyond the curtilage of the building and the civil engineering works. NOTE 2 The sustainability assessment in the standards developed under this framework encompasses potential impacts e.g. intrinsic hazards from chemicals that are not based on a full environmental risk assessment. The assessment of environmental, social and economic aspects of organizations, such as management systems, are not included in the standards developed under this framework. However, the decisions or actions that influence the environmental, social and economic performance of the object of assessment can be taken into account where the assessment includes management process related aspects.	published	Mandate: M/350 Amdt	<u>CEN/TC 350</u>
<u>EN 15804</u>	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction products	E	This European standard provides core product category rules (PCR) for Type III environmental declarations for any construction product and construction service. NOTE The assessment of social and economic performances at product level is not covered by this standard. The core PCR: - defines the parameters to be declared and the way in which they are collated and reported, - describes which stages of a product's life cycle are considered in the EPD and which processes are to be included in the life cycle stages, - defines rules for the development of scenarios, - includes the rules for calculating	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/350, M/350 Amdt	<u>CEN/TC 350</u>

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			the Life Cycle Inventory and the Life Cycle Impact Assessment underlying the EPD, including the specification of the data quality to be applied, - includes the rules for reporting predetermined, environmental and health information, that is not covered by LCA for a product, construction process and construction service where necessary, - defines the conditions under which construction products can be compared based on the information provided by EPD. For the EPD of construction services the same rules and requirements apply as for the EPD of construction products.			
EN 15804:2012+A2:2019/AC:2021	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction products	E	(see EN 15804)	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/350, M/350 Amdt	CEN/TC 350
EN 15942	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Communication format business-to-business	E	This document is applicable to all construction products and services related to buildings and construction works. It specifies and describes the communication format for the information defined in EN 15804 for business-to-business communication to ensure a common understanding through consistent communication of information. NOTE This document does not deal with business-to-consumer communication and is not intended for that purpose. Business-to-consumer communication format is planned to be the subject of a future document	published	Mandate: M/350	CEN/TC 350
EN 16309:2014+A1:2014	Sustainability of construction works - Assessment of social performance of buildings - Calculation methodology	E	This European Standard is one part of a suite of European Standards. The standard provides the specific methods and requirements for the assessment of social performance of a building while taking into account the building's functionality and technical characteristics. This European Standard applies to all types of buildings, both new and existing. In this first version of the standard, the social dimension of sustainability concentrates on the assessment of aspects and impacts for the use stage of a building expressed using the following social performance categories (from EN 15643 3): - accessibility; - adaptability; - health and comfort; - impacts on the neighbourhood; - maintenance; - safety and security. NOTE 1 Only impacts and aspects of the above social performance categories are deemed to have an agreed basis for European standardization at this time. Two of the social performance categories included in EN 15643-3 (sourcing of materials and services and stakeholder involvement) are not deemed to be ready for standardization at this time and will be considered for inclusion in future versions of this standard (see informative Annex C). This standard does not set the rules for	published		CEN/TC 350

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			<p>how building assessment schemes may provide valuation methods. Nor does it prescribe levels, classes or benchmarks of performance. Valuation methods, levels, classes or benchmarks may be prescribed in the requirements for environmental, social and economic performance in the client's brief, building regulations, national standards, national codes of practice, building assessment and certification schemes, etc. NOTE 2 Where National building regulations give minimum requirements and reference to assessment methods on these aspects, the social performance determined by assessment according to this standard can be used to determine the degree to which the building goes beyond the regulatory/legal requirements. The corporate social responsibility (CSR) of organizations is not covered by this standard. The standard gives requirements for: - the description of the object of assessment; - the system boundary that applies at the building level; - the list of indicators and procedures for the application of these indicators; - the presentation of the results in reporting and communication; - the data necessary for the application of the standard, and - verification.</p>			
EN 16627	Sustainability of construction works - Assessment of economic performance of buildings - Calculation methods	E	<p>This European Standard specifies the calculation methods, based on Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and other quantified economic information, to assess the economic performance of a building, and gives the means for the reporting and communication of the outcome of the assessment. This European Standard is applicable to new and existing buildings and refurbishment projects. This European Standard gives: - the description of the object of assessment; - the system boundary that applies at the building level; - the scope and procedure to be used for the analysis; - the list of indicators and procedures for the calculations of these indicators; - the requirements for presentation of the results in reporting and communication; - and the requirements for the data necessary for the calculation. The approach to the assessment covers all stages of the building life cycle and includes all building related construction products, processes and services, used over the life cycle of the building. The interpretation and value judgments of the results of the assessment are not within the scope of this European Standard.</p>	published		CEN/TC 350
EN 17472	Sustainability of construction works - Sustainability assessment of civil engineering works - Calculation methods	E	<p>This document establishes the requirements and specific methods for the assessment of environmental, economic and social performances of a civil engineering works while taking into account the civil engineering works' functionality and technical characteristics. By the means of this document the decision making for a project is supported by providing a</p>	published	Mandate: M/526	CEN/TC 350

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			standardized method for enabling comparability of scheme options. The assessment of environmental and economic performances of a civil engineering works is based on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Cost (LCC), Whole-Life Cost (WLC) and other quantified environmental and economic information. The approach to the assessment covers all stages of the civil engineering works life cycle and includes all civil engineering works related construction products, processes and services, used over its life cycle. This document is applicable to new and existing civil engineering works and refurbishment projects. The environmental performance is based on data obtained from Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) and additional indicators. This document is not applicable for the assessment of the environmental, social and economic performance of building(s) as part of the civil engineering works; instead, EN 15978, EN 16309 and EN 16627 apply.			
EN ISO 22057	Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works - Data templates for the use of environmental product declarations (EPDs) for construction products in building information modelling (BIM) (ISO 22057:2022)	E, I	This document provides the principles and requirements to enable environmental and technical data provided in EPDs for construction products and services, construction elements and integrated technical systems to be used in BIM to assist in the assessment of the environmental performance of a construction works over its life cycle. This document gives requirements on structuring EPD information using a data template according to ISO 23386 and ISO 23387, to make EPD data machine-interpretable and to enable their integration into information-driven design, construction, use and end-of-life stages. This document is applicable to structuring generic LCA data for use within a BIM environment, as these data are required in the absence of suitable EPD data to enable assessment of the environmental performance at the construction works level. The assessment of environmental performance at the construction works level is not covered by this document.	published		CEN/TC 350
CEN/TS 17459	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Determination of ecotoxicity of construction product eluates	E	(1) This document specifies a test procedure that combines horizontal leaching tests with ecotoxicity tests for the assessment of eluates of the construction products specified in this scope subjected to wet conditions in outdoor use. (2) The method specified in this document is intended for the determination of the potential ecotoxicity of eluates extracted out of construction products containing constitutional organic components of main categories of product matrices P (plastics and rubbers), A (sealants and adhesives) or C (paints and coatings) according to CEN/TR 16045. (3) Construction products mainly made of inorganic materials: main categories of product matrices S (silica-based and calcareous products)	published		CEN/TC 351

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			and M (metals) according to CEN/TR 16045 are excluded, unless - the liquid or paste product hardens in direct contact with soil or groundwater and - the used binder contains > 50 % organics by mass. NOTE 1 This exception mainly refers to products used for soil injection and stabilization, e.g. grouts. Also, the method is not intended for construction products made of treated or untreated solid wood in main category of product matrix W (wood-based products) according to CEN/TR 16045. For engineered bio-based products the test procedure can be of interest. (4) This document is not applicable for the assessment of terrestrial ecotoxicity of construction products. NOTE 2 Terrestrial ecotoxicity tests for construction products are described in CEN/TR 17105.			
<u>prCEN/TR XXX (WI00351055)</u>	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Specific quality assurance measures	E	The Technical report assesses the need for specific quality assurance measures for the test methods which have been developed by CEN/TC 351/WG 1 and CEN/TC 351/WG 5. It shows which measures could be taken and demonstrates their effectiveness	under drafting	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	<u>CEN/TC 351</u>
<u>prCEN/TR XXX (WI00351056)</u>	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Pros and cons of methods for communicating the potential release of dangerous substances into soil, groundwater or surface water and indoor air	E	This Technical Report describes the pros and cons of the different methods for reporting the potential release of dangerous substances into soil, groundwater or surface water and indoor air, which are: — level (or declared values); and — classes; as defined in the Construction Products Regulation (CPR). In addition, the pros and cons of additional methods based on discussion in CEN/TCs and WGs are described, which are: — categories, and — manufacturer's statement.	under drafting	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	<u>CEN/TC 351</u>
<u>prCEN/TR XXX (WI00351054)</u>	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Guidance for a broader application of the CEN/TC 351 reference room	E	To provide a concise overview of the following aspects of the application of reference rooms for the evaluation of emissions from products in indoor environments; European dimension of the scope (regulations and schemes) Evaluation of VOC emissions from building products: principles Background history Implementation in national regulations Implementation in voluntary schemes Broader application of the reference room (in addition to construction products) Other possible dimensions of a reference room Conclusion and references	under drafting	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	<u>CEN/TC 351</u>
<u>prCEN/TR XXX (WI00351042)</u>	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Methods for the determination of N-nitrosamines in air	E	The described method is suitable for the determination of N-nitrosamines in air samples derived from a test according to EN 16516. This method permits the determination of N-nitrosamines concentrations in the reference room defined in EN 16516.	under drafting	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	<u>CEN/TC 351</u>

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	samples derived by EN 16516					
prEN 16637-1	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Part 1: Guidance for the determination of leaching tests and additional testing steps	E	(1) This document allows the identification of the appropriate leaching test method for the determination of the release of RDS from construction products into soil, surface water and groundwater. This document provides a stepwise procedure for the determination of appropriate release tests, including: a) determination of the test method based on general product properties; b) choice of the test method using specific product properties. (2) Furthermore, this document gives general guidance for CEN Technical Product Committees and EOTA WGs on basic aspects (sampling, sample preparation and storage, eluate treatment, analysis of eluates and documentation) to be specified in the relevant product standards or ETAs. (3) Metallic products and coatings on metallic products are not considered in the determination scheme of this document since the test methods in prEN 16637 2:—1) (tank test) and prEN 16637 3:—2) (column test) are not appropriate for the testing of these construction products due to a different release mechanism (solubility control). NOTE See Annex F. (4) It is assumed that intermittent contact with water (e.g. exposure to rainwater) is tested – by convention – as permanent contact. For some coatings, (e.g. some renders with organic binders according to EN 15824 [7]) in intermittent contact to water, physical and chemical properties might be altered in permanent contact with water. These products are not considered in the determination scheme of this document since the test method in prEN 16637 2 is not appropriate for the testing of these construction products (in this case EN 16105 [8] might be an alternative method).	under approval	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
prEN 16637-2	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Part 2: Horizontal dynamic surface leaching test	E	(1) This document specifies a dynamic surface leaching test (DSLTL) which is aimed at determining the release per unit surface area as a function of time of inorganic and/or non-volatile organic substances from a monolithic, plate- or sheet-like product, when it is put into contact with an aqueous solution (leachant). The test method is not suitable for substances that are volatile under ambient conditions. (2) This test is a parameter specific test focusing on identifying and specifying parameter specific properties tested under specified conditions. It is not aimed at simulating real situations. The application of results to specific intended conditions of use may be established by means of modelling (not included in this document). (3) The test method applies to more or less regularly shaped test portions consisting of monolithic test pieces with minimum dimensions of 40 mm in all directions (volume > 64 000 mm ³ (64 cm ³)). It also applies to plate- or sheet-like products with surface areas of minimum	under approval	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

			<p>10 000 mm² (100 cm²) exposed to the leachant. Products designed to drain water (e.g. draining tiles, porous asphalt) and monolithic granular products according to prEN 16637 1:— 1), Table 1, are also tested by this test method. All products to be tested are assumed to maintain their integrity over a time frame relevant for the considered intended use. (4) The modification for granular construction products with low hydraulic conductivity (Annex A) applies for granular particles with so little drainage capacity between the grains that percolation in percolation tests and in practice is nearly impossible. (5) Metals, metallic coatings and organic coatings on metals are excluded from the scope of this document because the principles of this test (diffusion) are not obeyed by these products. Guidance on the need for testing of these products is under consideration. (6) For some coatings (e.g. some renders with organic binders according to EN 15824 [9]) in intermittent contact to water, physical and chemical properties might be changed in permanent contact with water. For these products this document is not appropriate. (7) Guidance on the applicability of the test method to a given product is outlined in prEN 16637 1. NOTE 1 This test method is only applicable if the product is chemically stable and the matrix does not dissolve. For construction products that are possibly used in contact with water this is usually not the case as construction products are then supposed to be dimensionally stable. If a product possibly wears substantially in its intended use, the test cannot provide proper information. If the product contains a substantial amount of water-soluble compounds, e.g. gypsum or anhydrite, the matrix could (partially) dissolve and lead to dimensional instability of the test piece. In this case the test standard also cannot be used. NOTE 2 Volatile organic substances include the low molecular weight substances in mixtures such as mineral oil. NOTE 3 It is not always possible to optimize test conditions simultaneously for inorganic and organic substances. Optimum test conditions can also vary between different groups of organic substances. Test requirements for organic substances are generally more stringent than those for inorganic substances. The test conditions suitable for measuring the release of organic substances will generally also be applicable to inorganic substances.</p>			
prEN 16637-3	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Part 3: Horizontal up-flow percolation test	E	(1) This document specifies an up-flow percolation test (PT) which is applicable to determine the leaching behaviour of inorganic and non-volatile organic substances from granular construction products. The test is not suitable for substances that are volatile under ambient conditions. The construction products are subjected to percolation with water as a function	under approval	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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			<p>of liquid to solid ratio under specified percolation conditions. The method is a once-through column leaching test. (2) This up-flow percolation test is performed under specified test conditions for construction products and does not necessarily produce results that mimic specific intended use conditions. This test method produces eluates, which can subsequently be characterized by physical, chemical and ecotoxicological methods according to existing standard methods. The results of eluate analysis are presented as a function of the liquid/solid ratio. The test results enable the distinction between different leaching behaviour. NOTE 1 Volatile organic substances include the low molecular weight substances in mixtures such as mineral oil. NOTE 2 It is not always possible to adjust test conditions simultaneously for inorganic and organic substances. Test conditions can also vary between different groups of organic substances. Test conditions for organic substances are generally more stringent than those for inorganic substances. The test conditions are generally described in a way that they fit testing organic substances and are also applicable to inorganic substances depending on the set-up. NOTE 3 For ecotoxicity testing, eluates representing the release of both inorganic and organic substances are needed. In this document, ecotoxicological testing is meant to include also genotoxicological testing. NOTE 4 Construction products with a low hydraulic conductivity that can cause detrimental pressure build-up are not supposed to be subjected to this test. NOTE 5 This procedure is generally not applicable to products that are easily biologically degradable and products reacting with the leachant, leading, for example, to excessive gas emission or excessive heat release, impermeable hydraulically bound products or products that swell in contact with water. (3) In this document the same test conditions as for prEN 17516 (CEN/TC 444/WG 1) are applied in order to allow full comparability of testing construction products and waste derived construction products to avoid double testing. The prEN 17516 test results are eligible in the context of testing construction products as well. NOTE 6 If a leaching test according to prEN 17516 has been performed, additional prEN 16637 3 testing does not need to be carried out.</p>			
prEN 17195	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Analysis of inorganic substances in eluates	E	This document specifies analytical methods for the determination of major, minor and trace elements and of anions in aqueous eluates from construction products. It refers to the following 67 elements: Aluminium (Al), antimony (Sb), arsenic (As), barium (Ba), beryllium (Be), bismuth (Bi), boron (B), cadmium (Cd), calcium (Ca), cerium (Ce), caesium (Cs), chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), dysprosium (Dy),	under approval	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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			erbium (Er), europium (Eu), gadolinium (Gd), gallium (Ga), germanium (Ge), gold (Au), hafnium (Hf), holmium (Ho), indium (In), iridium (Ir), iron (Fe), lanthanum (La), lead (Pb), lithium (Li), lutetium (Lu), magnesium (Mg), manganese (Mn), mercury (Hg), molybdenum (Mo), neodymium (Nd), nickel (Ni), palladium (Pd), phosphorus (P), platinum (Pt), potassium (K), praseodymium (Pr), rubidium (Rb), rhenium (Re), rhodium (Rh), ruthenium (Ru), samarium (Sm), scandium (Sc), selenium (Se), silicon (Si), silver (Ag), sodium (Na), strontium (Sr), sulphur (S), tellurium (Te), terbium (Tb), thallium (Tl), thorium (Th), thulium (Tm), tin (Sn), titanium (Ti), tungsten (W), uranium (U), vanadium (V), ytterbium (Yb), yttrium (Y), zinc (Zn), and zirconium (Zr) and to the following four anions: Cl-, Br-, F-, SO42-. This document also describes how to measure general parameters like pH, electrical conductivity, DOC/TOC. The methods in this document are applicable to construction products. NOTE Construction products include e.g. mineral-based products (S); bituminous products (B); metals (M); wood-based products (W); plastics and rubbers (P); sealants and adhesives (A); paints and coatings (C), see also CEN/TR 16045. The selection of analytical methods to be applied is based on the required sensitivity of the method, which is provided for all substance - analytical procedure combinations.			
prEN 17196	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Digestion by aqua regia for subsequent analysis of inorganic substances	E	This document specifies methods for obtaining the aqua regia digestible content of construction products. Solutions produced by this method are for analysis by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) and inductively coupled spectrometry (ICP-OES) for the following 67 elements: Aluminium (Al), antimony (Sb), arsenic (As), barium (Ba), beryllium (Be), bismuth (Bi), boron (B), cadmium (Cd), calcium (Ca), cerium (Ce), caesium (Cs), chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), dysprosium (Dy), erbium (Er), europium (Eu), gadolinium (Gd), gallium (Ga), germanium (Ge), gold (Au), hafnium (Hf), holmium (Ho), indium (In), iridium (Ir), iron (Fe), lanthanum (La), lead (Pb), lithium (Li), lutetium (Lu), magnesium (Mg), manganese (Mn), mercury (Hg), molybdenum (Mo), neodymium (Nd), nickel (Ni), palladium (Pd), phosphorus (P), platinum (Pt), potassium (K), praseodymium (Pr), rubidium (Rb), rhenium (Re), rhodium (Rh), ruthenium (Ru), samarium (Sm), scandium (Sc), selenium (Se), silicon (Si), silver (Ag), sodium (Na), strontium (Sr), sulphur (S), tellurium (Te), terbium (Tb), thallium (Tl), thorium (Th), thulium (Tm), tin (Sn), titanium (Ti), tungsten (W), uranium (U), vanadium (V), ytterbium (Yb), yttrium (Y), zinc (Zn), and zirconium (Zr). Solutions produced by the methods are suitable for analysis by cold vapour atomic absorption or	under approval	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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			fluorescent spectrometry (CV-AAS, CV-AFS), for mercury (Hg). The method in this document is applicable to construction products. Digestion with aqua regia will not necessarily accomplish total decomposition of the sample. The extracted analyte concentrations might not necessarily reflect the total content in the sample. NOTE Construction products include e.g. mineral-based products (S); bituminous products (B); metals (M); wood-based products (W); plastics and rubbers (P); sealants and adhesives (A); paints and coatings (C), see also CEN/TR 16045.			
prEN 17197	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Analysis of inorganic substances in digests and eluates - Analysis by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES)	E	This document specifies the method for the determination of major, minor and trace elements in aqua regia and nitric acid digests and in eluates of construction products by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES). It refers to the following 44 elements: Aluminium (Al), antimony (Sb), arsenic (As), barium (Ba), beryllium (Be), bismuth (Bi), boron (B), cadmium (Cd), calcium (Ca), cerium (Ce), chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), iron (Fe), lanthanum (La), lead (Pb), lithium (Li), magnesium (Mg), manganese (Mn), mercury (Hg), molybdenum (Mo), neodymium (Nd), nickel (Ni), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), praseodymium (Pr), samarium (Sm), scandium (Sc), selenium (Se), silicon (Si), silver (Ag), sodium (Na), strontium (Sr), sulphur (S), tellurium (Te), thallium (Tl), thorium (Th), tin (Sn), titanium (Ti), tungsten (W), uranium (U), vanadium (V), zinc (Zn), and zirconium (Zr). For the determination of low levels of As, Se and Sb, hydride generation can be applied. This method is described in Annex E. NOTE Construction products include e.g. mineral-based products (S); bituminous products (B); metals (M); wood-based products (W); plastics and rubbers (P); sealants and adhesives (A); paints and coatings (C), see also CEN/TR 16045. The method in this document is applicable to construction products and validated for the product types listed in Annex C.	under approval	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
prEN 17200	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Analysis of inorganic substances in digests and eluates - Analysis by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)	E	This document specifies the method for the determination of major, minor and trace elements in aqua regia and nitric acid digests and in eluates of construction products by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). It refers to the following 67 elements: aluminium (Al), antimony (Sb), arsenic (As), barium (Ba), beryllium (Be), bismuth (Bi), boron (B), cadmium (Cd), calcium (Ca), cerium (Ce), caesium (Cs), chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), dysprosium (Dy), erbium (Er), europium (Eu), gadolinium (Gd), gallium (Ga), germanium (Ge), gold (Au), hafnium (Hf), holmium (Ho), indium (In), iridium (Ir), iron (Fe), lanthanum (La), lead (Pb), lithium (Li), lutetium (Lu), magnesium (Mg), manganese (Mn), mercury (Hg), molybdenum (Mo), neodymium (Nd), nickel (Ni), palladium (Pd), phosphorus (P), platinum (Pt), potassium (K),	under approval	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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			<p>praseodymium (Pr), rubidium (Rb), rhenium (Re), rhodium (Rh), ruthenium (Ru), samarium (Sm), scandium (Sc), selenium (Se), silicon (Si), silver (Ag), sodium (Na), strontium (Sr), sulphur (S), tellurium (Te), terbium (Tb), thallium (Tl), thorium (Th), thulium (Tm), tin (Sn), titanium (Ti), tungsten (W), uranium (U), vanadium (V), ytterbium (Yb), yttrium (Y), zinc (Zn), and zirconium (Zr). NOTE 1 Construction products include e.g. mineral-based products (S); bituminous products (B); metals (M); wood-based products (W); plastics and rubbers (P); sealants and adhesives (A); paints and coatings (C), see also CEN/TR 16045 [1]. The working range depends on the matrix and the interferences encountered. NOTE 2 The limit of detection of most elements will be affected by their natural abundance, ionization behaviour, on abundance of isotope(s) free from isobaric interferences and by contamination (e.g. handling and airborne). Handling contaminations are in many cases more important than airborne ones. The limit of detection will be higher in cases where the determination is likely to be interfered (see Clause 6) or in case of memory effects (see e.g. EN ISO 17294 1:2006). The method in this document is applicable to construction products and validated for the product types listed in Annex A.</p>			
prEN 17201	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Content of inorganic substances - Methods for analysis of aqua regia digests	E	<p>This document specifies analytical methods for the determination of major, minor and trace elements in aqua regia digests of construction products. It refers to the following 67 elements: Aluminium (Al), antimony (Sb), arsenic (As), barium (Ba), beryllium (Be), bismuth (Bi), boron (B), cadmium (Cd), calcium (Ca), cerium (Ce), cesium (Cs), chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), dysprosium (Dy), erbium (Er), europium (Eu), gadolinium (Gd), gallium (Ga), germanium (Ge), gold (Au), hafnium (Hf), holmium (Ho), indium (In), iridium (Ir), iron (Fe), lanthanum (La), lead (Pb), lithium (Li), lutetium (Lu), magnesium (Mg), manganese (Mn), mercury (Hg), molybdenum (Mo), neodymium (Nd), nickel (Ni), palladium (Pd), phosphorus (P), platinum (Pt), potassium (K), praseodymium (Pr), rubidium (Rb), rhenium (Re), rhodium (Rh), ruthenium (Ru), samarium (Sm), scandium (Sc), selenium (Se), silicon (Si), silver (Ag), sodium (Na), strontium (Sr), sulphur (S), tellurium (Te), terbium (Tb), thallium (Tl), thorium (Th), thulium (Tm), tin (Sn), titanium (Ti), tungsten (W), uranium (U), vanadium (V), ytterbium (Yb), yttrium (Y), zinc (Zn), and zirconium (Zr). The methods in this document are applicable to construction products. NOTE Construction products include e.g. mineral-based products (S); bituminous products (B); metals (M); wood-based products (W); plastics and rubbers (P); sealants and adhesives (A); paints and coatings (C), see also CEN/TR 16045 [1]. The selection of analytical methods to be</p>	under approval	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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			applied is based on the required sensitivity of the method, which is provided for all combinations of substance and analytical procedure.			
prEN 17216	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Determination of radium-226, thorium-232 and potassium-40 activity using gamma-ray spectrometry	E	This document describes a test method for the determination of the activity of the radionuclides radium-226, thorium-232 and potassium-40 in construction products using semiconductor gamma-ray spectrometry. This document describes sampling from a laboratory sample, sample preparation, and the sample measurement by semiconductor gamma-ray spectrometry. It includes background subtraction, energy and efficiency calibration, analysis of the spectrum, calculation of the activity concentrations with the associated uncertainties, the decision threshold and detection limit, and reporting of the results. The preparation of the laboratory sample from the initial product sample lies outside its scope and is described in product standards. This document is intended to be non product-specific in scope, however, there are a limited number of product-specific elements such as the preparation of the laboratory sample and drying of the test portion. The method is applicable to samples from products consisting of single or multiple material components.	under drafting	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
prEN 17331	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Content of organic substances - Methods for extraction and analysis	E	This document specifies existing methods for the determination of the content of specific organic substances in construction products. The following parameters are covered: BTEX, biocides, dioxins, furans and dioxin-like PCBs, mineral oil, nonylphenols, PAH, PCB, PCP, PBDE, and short-chain chlorinated paraffins. NOTE 1 Methods still under development or available at national level only are listed in Annex B for PFOS, PFOA, HBCD and EOX. The methods can be included in the normative text as soon as full EN standards are available. NOTE 2 Methods that have not been validated for construction products, because no suitable material was available at the time of the robustness validation, only are listed in Annex B. This applies to organotin compounds, phenols and phthalates. The methods listed in this document come from different fields and are expected to be suitable for organic substances in organic extracts from all types of constructions products. The methods in this document are validated for the product types listed in Annex A. NOTE 3 Construction products include, e.g. mineral-based products, bituminous products, wood-based products, polymer-based products and metals. This document includes analytical methods for all matrices except metals.	under approval	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
prEN 17332	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Analysis of	E	This document specifies existing methods for the determination of specific organic substances in aqueous eluates from leaching of construction products. The following parameters are covered: pH, electrical conductivity, biocides,	under approval	No citation expected for Directive	CEN/TC 351

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	organic substances in eluates		bisphenol A, BTEX, dioxins and furans, DOC, epichlorohydrin, mineral oil, nonylphenols, PAH, PBDE, PCB, dioxin-like PCB, PCP, phenols and phthalates. NOTE 1 Methods still under development or available at national level only are listed in Annex B for certain amines, AOX, and biocidal and plant protection products. NOTE 2 Methods that have not been validated for aqueous eluates from leaching of construction products, because no suitable material was available at the time of the robustness validation, only are listed in Annex B. This applies to organotin compounds. The methods in this document come from different fields, mainly the analysis of water, and are applicable for the eluates from construction products. They are validated for eluates of the product types listed in Annex A. NOTE 3 Construction products include, e.g. mineral-based products, bituminous products, wood-based products, polymer-based products and metals. This document includes analytical methods for all matrices except metals. The selection of the method to be applied is based on the product matrix and the required sensitivity.		305/2011; Mandate: M/366	
<u>EN 17637</u>	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Dose assessment of emitted gamma radiation	E	This document describes a calculation method to determine the indoor gamma dose from construction products. The method includes calculation of the indoor gamma dose from the individual construction product under its intended use, as well as the dose from the building taking consideration of multiple building materials where this is deemed necessary and any shielding from the terrestrial background. The calculation method builds on existing modelling principles for photon emission and absorption. Parameters of the modelling that are not product specific, such as room geometry, exposure coefficients, and conversion factors are predefined and form the underlying basis for the method in this EN. The choice for pre-defined model parameters is essential from a harmonization perspective, despite the fact that such parameters can vary considerably for every homeowner, building type, region or country. Typical examples are the exposure time, the location of exposure in the building, the terrestrial background radiation and the amounts and way the building materials are used in the building. The parameters are selected on the basis of international consensus, as laid down in ICRP, UNSCEAR, EU RP guidelines and other renowned publications. Product specific parameters such as density and thickness are specified in accordance with the product's intended use. In addition, the products' massic activities of 226Ra, 232Th and 40K are specified and obtained according to prEN 17216 (under development, [3]). The method provides a tiered approach with a basic approach intended for assessing individual construction products, followed by a	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	<u>CEN/TC 351</u>

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			<p>more refined approach to assess a complete building design. The former approach assumes an identical structure of building materials on all six surfaces of the model room, and where needed complemented with other building materials that form an intrinsic part of the product's intended use. The latter approach enables evaluation of a known building design. Here the user can specify the applied construction product to walls, floor or ceiling separately in accordance with the product's intended use. The indoor gamma dose from the individual construction product as well as the building is expressed in terms of an annual effective dose from gamma radiation in the indoor environment. The formulation of the indoor gamma dose in the building is consistent with the dose for indoor external exposure as stated under Article 75 of the Basic Safety Standards Directive. As a result, the described method enables assessment of the calculated annual dose of the building against the reference level as defined in the Basic Safety Standards Directive. The method is designed for assessment of mineral based building materials applied in bulk or superficially and used as a construction product in buildings. This includes any building materials that have been identified by EU member states as being of concern from a radiation protection point of view. The method is envisaged for use by producers of building materials, architects and building constructors as well as authorities. NOTE It is important to state that following the calculation of dose, any subsequent regulatory classification falls explicitly outside the scope of this method and is the responsibility of the relevant authorities.</p>			
prEN 17844	<p>Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Determination of the content of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) and of benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene and xylenes (BTEX) - Gas chromatographic method with mass spectrometric detection</p>	E	<p>This document describes two methods for determining the content of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) and one method for determining the content of benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene and xylenes (BTEX) with gas chromatography with mass spectrometric detection (GC-MS). See Annex A for a list of PAH and BTEX that can be determined with this document. This document is intended to be used for construction products. In a number of cases additional analysis with high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) can be necessary to determine a number of compounds. To determine PAH multiple liquid-liquid extraction is used to remove disturbing compounds. The tests that led to this document were carried out on different types of roofing material, asphalt and one tar containing asphalt, [3] and [5]. The detectability limit of the methods for individual compounds in roofing material, asphalt and tar containing asphalt for PAH is 0,5 mg/kg to 1,5 mg/kg and for BTEX 0,1 mg/kg.</p>	under approval	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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prEN 17845	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Determination of biocide residues using LC-MS/MS	E	This document describes a method for the determination of the content of biocides in construction products, (either finished (dried) or in a ready-to-use state) and in eluates thereof, using liquid chromatography and tandem mass spectrometric detection (LC-MS/MS). For content analysis liquid chromatography with UV-detection can also be used, if sufficient sensitivity and selectivity is ensured (see Annex A). The method in this document is validated for the product types listed in Annex D. For eluate analysis quantification limits of 0,1 µg/l can be achieved.	under approval	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
CEN/TR 15855	Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Barriers to trade	E	This Technical Report indicates the barriers to trade as identified by the product Technical Committees and other available sources in relation to release of regulated dangerous substances into indoor air, surface water, ground water or soil. This TR describes if and how these barriers to trade can be resolved or prevented by the standards included in the work programme of CEN/TC 351.	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
CEN/TR 15858	Construction products - Assessment of the release of regulated dangerous substances from construction products based on the WT, WFT/FT procedures	E	This CEN Technical Report describes a procedure for assessing construction products with regards to their release/emission of regulated dangerous substances (RDS) into the environment in accordance with Essential Requirement Number 3 of the Construction Products Directive (CPD), as far as these construction products fall under the responsibility of CEN. NOTE 1 For the purpose of this document and mandate M/366, the release of regulated dangerous substances from construction products is limited to two main environmental compartments: 1) soil, groundwater and surface water; 2) indoor air. NOTE 2 It should be noted that construction products falling under the CPD and these environmental compartments are the subject of other European Union regulations, e.g. REACH, and they may also be the subject of Member State regulations. This Technical Report defines how the mandated characteristics expressed in terms of mandated RDSs for each construction product can be assessed by an individual manufacturer using the 'Without Testing' (WT) procedure and/or the 'Without Further Testing' (WFT) and 'Further Testing' (FT) procedures after an initial type assessment and how the corresponding information accompanying the CE marking can be expressed in terms of declared values or RDS classes. This report describes: a) under which conditions a RDS class for a construction product may be declared by the individual manufacturer using the 'Without Testing (WT)' assessment procedure; b) if all relevant mandated RDSs are assessed by this Without Testing procedure, how a set of RDS classes for a construction product may also be declared by the manufacturer without the need for testing of their specific products; c) how to establish RDS	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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			classes for a construction product using a Without Further Testing procedure once sufficient information has been obtained from initial type testing; d) when and how to undertake Further Testing as part of factory production contro			
CEN/TR16045	Construction Products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Content of regulated dangerous substances - Selection of analytical methods	E	This Technical Report describes appropriate standard test methods for the determination of the content of regulated dangerous substances in construction products. Because of the similarity of the analytical methods for digests and eluates from leaching, the analysis of eluates from leaching is also covered. This Technical Report is relevant to all substances covered by the provisions of the main body of Mandate M/366, i.e. those included in the work programme for the emission into indoor air, and release to surface water, ground water and soil. The list of regulated substances provided by the Commission in document "Indicative list of regulated dangerous substances" [1] defines the substances, for which analytical methods for content will in principle be needed. This report will be limited to this list. NOTE 1 Sampling for content analysis is addressed by applying the relevant product standards and or by applying WI 00351013, Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Complement to sampling (TR 4) [7] in case the sampling protocol for technical properties does not adequately address requirements in testing posed by the assessment of release to soil, surface and groundwater. NOTE 2 Based on this selection of appropriate test methods from other fields, horizontal test methods for analysing the chemical content of construction products will be developed as ENs. NOTE 3 In Annex B a compilation is given of the content regulations for construction products for health or environmental reasons.	publishe d	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
CEN/TR16098	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Concept of horizontal testing procedures in support of requirements under the CPD	E	This Technical Report (TR), taking into account the state of the art in the Member States, identifies the role of testing in the assessment of construction products in view of possible emissions and makes recommendations on the testing procedures. This Technical Report reviews in accordance with the experience already gained, the basis for deciding whether the use of horizontal test method standards for construction products is practicable and/or necessary in order to implement obligations arising from the Construction Products Directive (CPD). The time limit for all information CEN/TC 351/TG 2 has been able to consider is set to be 31 December 2009. This Technical Report provides recommendations for complete testing procedures in the overall framework of the CPD according to the methods for the Attestation of Conformity (AoC).	publishe d	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
CEN/TR16220	Construction products - Assessment of release	E	This Technical Report covers the specific requirements for sampling construction products to determine the release or	publishe d	No citation expected for	CEN/TC 351

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	of dangerous substances - Complement to sampling		emission of dangerous substances in their intended use. It is complementary to existing sampling standards and sampling instruction in product standards or test methods for construction products of CEN product TCs and EOTA committees which fall under the CPD. The scope of this Technical Report covers all activities related to product sampling, starting with the initial planning of sampling until the delivery and formal transfer of the laboratory sample at the laboratory. This Technical Report: - does not deal with sub-sampling in the laboratory as a step towards the preparation of the test portion / test specimen); - does not deal with the second sampling domain in which a sample is to be taken from the air (emission) or water (release) with which the test portion / test specimen has been in contact; - does not deal with the statistical testing of a construction product against (legislative) limit values, nor does it deal with the definition of repetitive sampling, suitable for fulfilling requirements with respect to a minimum level of uncertainty in a series of test results. This Technical Report focuses on obtaining a single sample. Repetitive sampling is outside the scope as the boundary conditions for routine testing against a limit are not yet defined (e.g. the necessary reliability). Despite the fact that repetitive sampling is not covered, the conditions provided in this Technical Report apply for an individual sample, as well as for a sample that is part of a series.		Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	
CEN/TR16410	Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Barriers to use - Extension to CEN/TR 15855 Barriers to trade	E	This TR is an extension to CEN/TR 15855:2009. This original report on Barriers to Trade, prepared in response to Mandate M/366 given to CEN/TC 351 by the European Commission, identified that some of these barriers were truly technical or legal barriers to trade which can usually be overcome or minimised by technical harmonisation work, but others were quite legally in place, sometimes voluntary, but were nonetheless still seen as a barrier to the use of certain products in a free market place. This report is an examination of these concepts in more detail and an attempt to identify the reasons behind the presence of barriers to use and to present specific examples in more detail.	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011;	CEN/TC 351
CEN/TR16496	Construction Products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Use of harmonised horizontal assessment methods	E	This Technical Report (TR) provides step-by-step guidance for product Technical Committees (TCs) and EOTA Working Groups (WGs), on how the harmonized measurement/test methods can be integrated into technical specifications.	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
CEN/TR16797-1	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Guidance	E	This Technical Report provides guidance on the statistical assessment of declared values with respect to the release, emission and/or content of dangerous substances. This Technical Report provides statistically-based criteria for type-	published		CEN/TC 351

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	on the statistical assessment of declared values - Part 1: Principles and rules of application		testing (TT), further-testing (FT) and where a product has been shown to be consistent with measured values for the release, emission or content that are significantly below the declared values, the point where no-further-testing (NFT) is permitted. A series of fundamental principles are defined in the present document and two statistical approaches are defined. The first approach is to use assessment by variables and this approach requires the data to be normally or log-normally distributed. This approach is recommended as the default option. The alternative approach based on assessment by attributes is appropriate for data sets that are not normally or log-normally distributed. The downside to this form of assessment is that more test data are needed for the same level of reliability. The present document introduces these assessment procedures and CEN/TR 16797-2 provides more detail and the statistical proof that they satisfy the principles defined in this document. With both of these approaches the minimum frequency of testing is a function of the distance between the mean value and declared value and the variability of the data set, i.e. the sample standard deviation. To reduce the costs of testing, production plants producing a similar product may share data, e.g. be grouping the product into clusters for statistical assessment of declared values. Rules for the use of clusters are given in CEN/TR 16797-2. CEN/TR 16797-2 also contains rules for identifying outliers within a data set and guidance on using tests other than the reference method for FT. A list of tasks for product technical committees is given in CEN/TR 16797-2 as is a model clause for including in product standards and rules of applications that may be cited in the product standard or copied into product standards.			
CEN/TR 16797-2	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Guidance on the statistical assessment of declared values - Part 2: Technical and statistical background	E	This Technical Report provides guidance on the statistical assessment of declared values with respect to the release, emission and/or content of dangerous substances. This report provides statistically-based criteria for type-testing (TT), further-testing (FT) and where a product has been shown to be consistent with measured values for the release, emission or content that are significantly below the declared values, the point where no-further-testing (NFT) is permitted. A series of fundamental principles are defined in CEN/TR 16797-1 and two statistical approaches are defined. The first approach is to use assessment by variables and this approach requires the data to be normally or log-normally distributed. This approach is recommended as the default option. The alternative approach based on assessment by attributes is appropriate for data sets that are not normally or log-normally distributed. The downside to this form of assessment is that more test data are needed for the same level of reliability. CEN/TR 16797-1	published		CEN/TC 351

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			introduces these assessment procedures and CEN/TR 16797-2 provides more detail and the statistical proof that they satisfy the principles defined in CEN/TR 16797-1. With both of these approaches the minimum frequency of testing is a function of the distance between the mean value and declared value and the variability of the data set, i.e. the sample standard deviation. To reduce the costs of testing, production plants producing a similar product may share data, e.g. be grouping the product into clusters for statistical assessment of declared values. Rules for the use of clusters are given in this document. This document also contains rules for identifying outliers within a data set and guidance on using tests other than the reference method for FT. A list of tasks for product technical committees is given in this document as is a model clause for including in product standards and rules of applications that may be cited in the product standard or copied into product standards.			
CEN/TR 17105	Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Guidance on the use of ecotoxicity tests applied to construction products	E	This Technical Report gives information on existing methods to test ecotoxicity of construction products. Information is given on how to combine recommended leaching tests with biological tests for the aquatic environment and how to avoid possible problems, when performing biological tests. Also suitable terrestrial tests on granular construction products diluted with artificial soil are proposed for a minimum test battery. Reference has been made as far as possible to existing International and European Standards and guidelines. The test procedure described in this Technical Report is technically suitable for all construction product eluates and for terrestrial tests on granular or paste-like construction products. However, from the point of view of test efficiency it is recommended mainly for products containing organics or polymers in case chemical analysis alone is not deemed to be sufficient. For inorganic products the chemical analysis is seen as straightforward in construction product eluates and therefore the added value of data received through ecotoxicity tests is seen as limited.	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
CEN/TR 17113	Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Radiation from construction products - Dose assessment of emitted gamma radiation	E	The aim of this Technical Report is to propose a methodology to determine indoor gamma dose from building materials and to help classify such a product as required in the Construction Products Regulation [7]. This first technical approach could be a precursor for the development of a harmonized European Standard based on this methodology. NOTE 1 In this Technical Report, doses from radon and thoron exhalation are excluded. However, in 3.3, information is given on how radon exhalation is dealt with in (EU)2013/59/Euratom, the Basic Safety Standards Directive (2013/59/EURATOM) [1]. NOTE 2	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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			Compliance with national exemption levels for NORM nuclides remains.			
CEN/TR17304	Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Determination of emissions into indoor air of ammonia from cellulose insulation at 90 % RH	E	This Technical Report specifies a method for the determination of ammonia from cellulose insulation products at 90% relative humidity (RH). This document is based on the existing prEN 16516 standard which provides an horizontal reference method for the determination of emissions of regulated dangerous substances from construction products into indoor air.	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
CEN/TS 16637-1	Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Part 1: Guidance for the determination of leaching tests and additional testing steps	E	(1) This document allows the identification of the appropriate leaching test method for the determination of the release of RDS from construction products into soil, surface water and groundwater. This document provides a stepwise procedure for the determination of appropriate release tests, including: a) determination of the test method based on general product properties; b) choice of the test method using specific product properties. (2) Furthermore, this Technical Specification gives general guidance for CEN Technical Product Committees and EOTA WGs on basic aspects (sampling, sample preparation and storage, eluate treatment, analysis of eluates and documentation) to be specified in the relevant product standards or ETAs. (3) Metallic products and coatings on metallic products are not considered in the determination scheme of this Technical Specification since the test methods in CEN/TS 16637-2 (tank test) and CEN/TS 16637-3 (column test) are not appropriate for the testing of these construction products due to a different release mechanism (solubility control). NOTE See Annex F. (4) It is assumed that intermittent contact with water (e. g. exposure to rainwater) is tested — by convention — as permanent contact. For some coatings, (e. g. some renders with organic binders according to EN 15824 [4]) in intermittent contact to water, physical and chemical properties might be altered in permanent contact with water. These products are not considered in the determination scheme of this Technical Specification since the test method in CEN/TS 16637-2 is not appropriate for the testing of these construction products (in this case EN 16105 [5] might be an alternative method).	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
CEN/TS 16637-2	Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Part 2: Horizontal dynamic surface leaching test	E	(1) This Technical Specification specifies a Dynamic Surface Leaching Test (DSLTL) which is aimed at determining the release per unit surface area as a function of time of inorganic and/or non-volatile organic substances from a monolithic, plate- or sheet-like product, when it is put into contact with an aqueous solution (leachant). The test method is not suitable for substances that are volatile under ambient conditions. (2)	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

		<p>This test is a parameter specific test focusing on identifying and specifying parameter specific properties tested under specified conditions. It is not aimed at simulating real situations. The application of results to specific intended conditions of use may be established by means of modelling (not included in this Technical Specification). (3) The modification for granular construction products with low hydraulic conductivity (Annex A) applies for granular particles with so little drainage capacity between the grains that percolation in percolation tests and in practice is nearly impossible. (4) The test method applies to more or less regularly shaped test portions consisting of monolithic test pieces with minimum dimensions of 40 mm in all directions (volume > 64 000 mm³ (64 cm³)). It also applies to plate- or sheet-like products with surface areas of minimum 10 000 mm² (100 cm²) exposed to the leachant. Products designed to drain water (e.g. draining tiles, porous asphalt) and monolithic granular products according to CEN/TS 16637-1:2014, Table 1, are also tested by this test method. All products to be tested are assumed to maintain their integrity over a time frame relevant for the considered intended use. (5) Metals, metallic coatings and organic coatings on metals are excluded from the scope of CEN/TS 16637-2 because the principles of this test (diffusion) are not obeyed by these products. Guidance on the need for testing of these products is under consideration. (6) For some coatings (e.g. some renders with organic binders according to EN 15824) in intermittent contact to water, physical and chemical properties might be changed in permanent contact with water. For these products CEN/TS 16637-2 is not appropriate. (7) Guidance on the applicability of the test method to a given product is outlined in CEN/TS 16637-1. NOTE 1 This test method is only applicable if the product is chemically stable and the matrix does not dissolve. For construction products that may be used in contact with water this usually should not be the case as construction products should then be dimensionally stable. If a product may substantially wear in its intended use, the test cannot provide proper information. If the product contains a substantial amount of water-soluble compounds, e.g. gypsum or anhydrite, the matrix may (partially) dissolve and lead to dimensional instability of the test piece. In this case the test standard also cannot be used. NOTE 2 Volatile organic substances include the low molecular weight substances in mixtures such as mineral oil. NOTE 3 It is not always possible to optimise test conditions simultaneously for inorganic and organic substances and optimum test conditions may also vary between different groups of organic substances. Test</p>			
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			requirements for organic substances are generally more stringent than those for inorganic substances. The test conditions suitable for measuring the release of organic substances will generally also be applicable to inorganic substances.			
CEN/TS 16637-3	Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Part 3: Horizontal up-flow percolation test	E	(1) This Technical Specification specifies an Up-flow Percolation Test (PT) which is applicable to determine the leaching behaviour of inorganic and non-volatile organic substances from granular construction products. The test is not suitable for substances that are volatile under ambient conditions. The construction products are subjected to percolation with water as a function of liquid to solid ratio under specified percolation conditions. The method is a once-through column leaching test. (2) This up-flow percolation test is performed under specified test conditions for construction products and does not necessarily produce results that mimic specific intended use conditions. This test method produces eluates, which can subsequently be characterized by physical, chemical and ecotoxicological methods according to existing standard methods. The results of eluate analysis are presented as a function of the liquid/solid ratio. The test results enable the distinction between different leaching behaviour. NOTE 1 Volatile organic substances include the low molecular weight substances in mixtures such as mineral oil. NOTE 2 It is not always possible to adjust test conditions simultaneously for inorganic and organic substances and test conditions may also vary between different groups of organic substances. Test conditions for organic substances are generally more stringent than those for inorganic substances. The test conditions are generally described in a way that they fit testing organic substances and are also applicable to inorganic substances depending on the set-up. NOTE 3 For ecotoxicity testing, eluates representing the release of both inorganic and organic substances are needed. In this document, ecotoxicological testing is meant to include also genotoxicological testing. Construction products that exhibit a saturated hydraulic conductivity of about 10 ⁻⁸ m/s or higher can usually be subjected to this test. This procedure is also applicable to materials showing solidification in the column, if the final hydraulic conductivity is within the specified range. Inert granular material should not be added to improve permeability in order to enable their testing. NOTE 4 This procedure is generally not applicable to products that are easily biologically degradable and products reacting with the leachant, leading, for example, to excessive gas emission or excessive heat release, impermeable hydraulically bound products or products that swell in contact with water.	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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CEN/TS 17195	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Analysis of inorganic substances in eluates	E	This Technical Specification specifies analytical methods for the determination of major, minor and trace elements and of anions in aqueous eluates from construction products. It refers to the following 67 elements: Aluminium (Al), antimony (Sb), arsenic (As), barium (Ba), beryllium (Be), bismuth (Bi), boron (B), cadmium (Cd), calcium (Ca), cerium (Ce), cesium (Cs), chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), dysprosium (Dy), erbium (Er), europium (Eu), gadolinium (Gd), gallium (Ga), germanium (Ge), gold (Au), hafnium (Hf), holmium (Ho), indium (In), iridium (Ir), iron (Fe), lanthanum (La), lead (Pb), lithium (Li), lutetium (Lu), magnesium (Mg), manganese (Mn), mercury (Hg), molybdenum (Mo), neodymium (Nd), nickel (Ni), palladium (Pd), phosphorus (P), platinum (Pt), potassium (K), praseodymium (Pr), rubidium (Rb), rhenium (Re), rhodium (Rh), ruthenium (Ru), samarium (Sm), scandium (Sc), selenium (Se), silicon (Si), silver (Ag), sodium (Na), strontium (Sr), sulphur (S), tellurium (Te), terbium (Tb), thallium (Tl), thorium (Th), thulium (Tm), tin (Sn), titanium (Ti), tungsten (W), uranium (U), vanadium (V), ytterbium (Yb), yttrium (Y), zinc (Zn), and zirconium (Zr) and to the following four anions: Cl-, Br-, F-, SO42-. The Technical Specification also describes how to measure general parameters like pH, electrical conductivity, DOC/TOC. The methods in this Technical Specification are applicable to construction products. NOTE Construction products include e.g. mineral-based products (S); bituminous products (B); metals (M); wood-based products (W); plastics and rubbers (P); sealants and adhesives (A); paints and coatings (C), see also CEN/TR 16045. The selection of analytical methods to be applied is based on the required sensitivity of the method, which is provided for all substance - analytical procedure combinations.	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
CEN/TS 17196	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Digestion by aqua regia for subsequent analysis of inorganic substances	E	This Technical Specification specifies methods for obtaining the aqua regia digestible content of construction products. Solutions produced by this method are for analysis by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) and inductively coupled spectrometry (ICP-OES) for the following 67 elements: Aluminium (Al), antimony (Sb), arsenic (As), barium (Ba), beryllium (Be), bismuth (Bi), boron (B), cadmium (Cd), calcium (Ca), cerium (Ce), cesium (Cs), chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), dysprosium (Dy), erbium (Er), europium (Eu), gadolinium (Gd), gallium (Ga), germanium (Ge), gold (Au), hafnium (Hf), holmium (Ho), indium (In), iridium (Ir), iron (Fe), lanthanum (La), lead (Pb), lithium (Li), lutetium (Lu), magnesium (Mg), manganese (Mn), mercury (Hg), molybdenum (Mo), neodymium (Nd), nickel (Ni), palladium (Pd), phosphorus (P), platinum (Pt), potassium (K), praseodymium (Pr), rubidium (Rb), rhenium (Re), rhodium	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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			(Rh), ruthenium (Ru), samarium (Sm), scandium (Sc), selenium (Se), silicon (Si), silver (Ag), sodium (Na), strontium (Sr), sulphur (S), tellurium (Te), terbium (Tb), thallium (Tl), thorium (Th), thulium (Tm), tin (Sn), titanium (Ti), tungsten (W), uranium (U), vanadium (V), ytterbium (Yb), yttrium (Y), zinc (Zn), and zirconium (Zr). Solutions produced by the methods are suitable for analysis by cold vapour atomic absorption or fluorescent spectrometry (CV-AAS, CV-AFS), for mercury (Hg). The method in this Technical Specification is applicable to construction products. Digestion with aqua regia will not necessarily accomplish total decomposition of the sample. The extracted analyte concentrations may not necessarily reflect the total content in the sample. NOTE Construction products include e.g. mineral-based products (S); bituminous products (B); metals (M); wood-based products (W); plastics and rubbers (P); sealants and adhesives (A); paints and coatings (C), see also CEN/TR 16045.			
CEN/TS 17197	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Analysis of inorganic substances in digests and eluates - Analysis by Inductively Coupled Plasma - Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES)	E	This Technical Specification specifies the method for the determination of major, minor and trace elements in aqua regia and nitric acid digests and in eluates of construction products by Inductively Coupled Plasma – Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES). It refers to the following 44 elements: Aluminium (Al), antimony (Sb), arsenic (As), barium (Ba), beryllium (Be), bismuth (Bi), boron (B), cadmium (Cd), calcium (Ca), cerium (Ce), chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), iron (Fe), lanthanum (La), lead (Pb), lithium (Li), magnesium (Mg), manganese (Mn), mercury (Hg), molybdenum (Mo), neodymium (Nd), nickel (Ni), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), praseodymium (Pr), samarium (Sm), scandium (Sc), selenium (Se), silicon (Si), silver (Ag), sodium (Na), strontium (Sr), sulphur (S), tellurium (Te), thallium (Tl), thorium (Th), tin (Sn), titanium (Ti), tungsten (W), uranium (U), vanadium (V), zinc (Zn), and zirconium (Zr). For the determination of low levels of As, Se and Sb, hydride generation may be applied. This method is described in Annex D. NOTE Construction products include e.g. mineral-based products (S); bituminous products (B); metals (M); wood-based products (W); plastics and rubbers (P); sealants and adhesives (A); paints and coatings (C), see also CEN/TR 16045 [1]. The method in this Technical Specification is applicable to construction products and validated for the product types listed in Annex D.	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
CEN/TS 17200	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Analysis of inorganic substances in digests and eluates -	E	This Technical Specification specifies the method for the determination of major, minor and trace elements in aqua regia and nitric acid digests and in eluates of construction products by Inductively Coupled Plasma - Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS). It refers to the following 67 elements: Aluminium (Al), antimony (Sb), arsenic (As), barium (Ba), beryllium (Be),	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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	Analysis by Inductively Coupled Plasma - Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS)		<p>bismuth (Bi), boron (B), cadmium (Cd), calcium (Ca), cerium (Ce), cesium (Cs), chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), dysprosium (Dy), erbium (Er), europium (Eu), gadolinium (Gd), gallium (Ga), germanium (Ge), gold (Au), hafnium (Hf), holmium (Ho), indium (In), iridium (Ir), iron (Fe), lanthanum (La), lead (Pb), lithium (Li), lutetium (Lu), magnesium (Mg), manganese (Mn), mercury (Hg), molybdenum (Mo), neodymium (Nd), nickel (Ni), palladium (Pd), phosphorus (P), platinum (Pt), potassium (K), praseodymium (Pr), rubidium (Rb), rhenium (Re), rhodium (Rh), ruthenium (Ru), samarium (Sm), scandium (Sc), selenium (Se), silicon (Si), silver (Ag), sodium (Na), strontium (Sr), sulphur (S), tellurium (Te), terbium (Tb), thallium (Tl), thorium (Th), thulium (Tm), tin (Sn), titanium (Ti), tungsten (W), uranium (U), vanadium (V), ytterbium (Yb), yttrium (Y), zinc (Zn), and zirconium (Zr). NOTE 1 Construction products include e.g. mineral-based products (S); bituminous products (B); metals (M); wood-based products (W); plastics and rubbers (P); sealants and adhesives (A); paints and coatings (C), see also CEN/TR 16045 [1]. The working range depends on the matrix and the interferences encountered. NOTE 2 The limit of detection of most elements will be affected by their natural abundance, ionization behaviour, on abundance of isotope(s) free from isobaric interferences and by contamination (e.g. handling and airborne). Handling contaminations are in many cases more important than airborne ones. The limit of detection will be higher in cases where the determination is likely to be interfered (see Clause 4) or in case of memory effects (see e.g. EN ISO 17294-1:2006, 8.2). The method in this Technical Specification is applicable to construction products and validated for the product types listed in Annex B.</p>			
CEN/TS 17201	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Content of inorganic substances - Methods for analysis of aqua regia digests	E	<p>This Technical Specification specifies analytical methods for the determination of major, minor and trace elements in aqua regia digests of construction products. It refers to the following 67 elements: Aluminium (Al), antimony (Sb), arsenic (As), barium (Ba), beryllium (Be), bismuth (Bi), boron (B), cadmium (Cd), calcium (Ca), cerium (Ce), cesium (Cs), chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), dysprosium (Dy), erbium (Er), europium (Eu), gadolinium (Gd), gallium (Ga), germanium (Ge), gold (Au), hafnium (Hf), holmium (Ho), indium (In), iridium (Ir), iron (Fe), lanthanum (La), lead (Pb), lithium (Li), lutetium (Lu), magnesium (Mg), manganese (Mn), mercury (Hg), molybdenum (Mo), neodymium (Nd), nickel (Ni), palladium (Pd), phosphorus (P), platinum (Pt), potassium (K), praseodymium (Pr), rubidium (Rb), rhenium (Re), rhodium (Rh), ruthenium (Ru), samarium (Sm), scandium (Sc), selenium (Se), silicon (Si), silver (Ag), sodium (Na), strontium (Sr), sulphur</p>	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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			(S), tellurium (Te), terbium (Tb), thallium (Tl), thorium (Th), thulium (Tm), tin (Sn), titanium (Ti), tungsten (W), uranium (U), vanadium (V), ytterbium (Yb), yttrium (Y), zinc (Zn), and zirconium (Zr). The methods in this Technical Specification are applicable to construction products. NOTE Construction products include e.g. mineral-based products (S); bituminous products (B); metals (M); wood-based products (W); plastics and rubbers (P); sealants and adhesives (A); paints and coatings (C), see also CEN/TR 16045 [1]. The selection of analytical methods to be applied is based on the required sensitivity of the method, which is provided for all combinations of substance and analytical procedure.			
CEN/TS 17216	Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Determination of activity concentrations of radium-226, thorium-232 and potassium-40 in construction products using semiconductor gamma-ray spectrometry	E	This document describes a test method for the determination of the activity concentrations of the radionuclides radium-226, thorium-232 and potassium-40 in construction products using semiconductor gamma-ray spectrometry. This document describes sampling from a laboratory sample, sample preparation, and the sample measurement by semiconductor gamma-ray spectrometry. It includes background subtraction, energy and efficiency calibration, analysis of the spectrum, calculation of the activity concentrations with the associated uncertainties, the decision threshold and detection limit, and reporting of the results. The preparation of the laboratory sample from the initial product sample lies outside its scope and is described in product standards. This document is intended to be non product-specific in scope, however, there are a limited number of product-specific elements such as the preparation of the laboratory sample and drying of the test portion. The method is applicable to samples from products consisting of single or multiple material components.	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
CEN/TS 17331	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Content of organic substances - Methods for extraction and analysis	E	This document specifies existing methods for the determination of the content of specific organic substances in construction products. The following parameters are covered: BTEX, biocides, dioxins, furans and dioxin-like PCBs, mineral oil, nonylphenols, PAH, PCB, PCP, PBDE, and short-chain chlorinated paraffins. NOTE 1 Methods still under development or available at national level only are listed in Annex B for PFOS, PFOA, HBCD and EOX. The methods can be included in the normative text as soon as full EN standards are available. NOTE 2 Methods that have not been validated for construction products, because no suitable material was available at the time of the robustness validation, only are listed in Annex B. This applies to organotin compounds, phenols and phthalates. The methods listed in this document come from different fields and are expected to be suitable for organic substances in organic extracts from all types of constructions products. The methods in this document are validated for the product	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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			types listed in Annex A. NOTE 3 Construction products include, e.g. mineral-based products, bituminous products, wood-based products, polymer-based products and metals. This document includes analytical methods for all matrices except metals.			
CEN/TS 17332	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Analysis of organic substances in eluates	E	This document specifies existing methods for the determination of specific organic substances in aqueous eluates from leaching of construction products. The following parameters are covered: pH, electrical conductivity, biocides, bisphenol A, BTEX, dioxins and furans, DOC, epichlorohydrin, mineral oil, nonylphenols, PAH, PBDE, PCB, dioxin-like PCB, PCP, phenols and phthalates. NOTE 1 Methods still under development or available at national level only are listed in Annex B for certain amines, AOX, and biocidal and plant protection products. NOTE 2 Methods that have not been validated for aqueous eluates from leaching of construction products, because no suitable material was available at the time of the robustness validation, only are listed in Annex B. This applies to organotin compounds. The methods in this document come from different fields, mainly the analysis of water, and are applicable for the eluates from construction products. They are validated for eluates of the product types listed in Annex A. NOTE 3 Construction products include, e.g. mineral-based products, bituminous products, wood-based products, polymer-based products and metals. This document includes analytical methods for all matrices except metals. The selection of the method to be applied is based on the product matrix and the required sensitivity.	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
EN 16516	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Determination of emissions into indoor air	E	This European Standard specifies a horizontal reference method for the determination of emissions of regulated dangerous substances from construction products into indoor air. This method is applicable to volatile organic compounds, semi-volatile organic compounds, and very volatile aldehydes. It is based on the use of a test chamber and subsequent analysis of the organic compounds by GC-MS or HPLC. NOTE 1 Supplemental information is given on indirect test methods (see Annex B) and on measuring very volatile organic compounds (see Annex C). NOTE 2 This European Standard describes the overall procedure and makes use of existing standards mainly by normative reference, complemented when necessary with additional or modified normative requirements.	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
EN 16687	Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Terminology	E	This European Standard defines terms used in the field of the assessment of the release, and the content, of dangerous substances from / in construction products. The terms are classified under the following main headings: - Terms related to products and substances (general; soil, groundwater and	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351

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			surface water; indoor air); - Terms related to sampling and sample preparation; - Terms related to test procedures and test results (general; soil, groundwater and surface water; indoor air, radiation). An alphabetical index is provided. NOTE Further terms generally concerning the development and application of technical specifications for construction products which fall under the scope of the construction products regulation (CPR) are listed in Annex A.			
EN 17087	Construction products: Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Preparation of test portions from the laboratory sample for testing of release and analysis of content	E	This document is applicable for the preparation of representative test portions from the laboratory sample that has been taken as specified in respective product standards and in CEN/TR 16220, prior to testing of release and analysis of content of construction products. This document is intended to specify the sequence of operations and treatments to be applied to the laboratory sample in order to obtain suitable test portions in compliance with the specific requirements defined in the corresponding test methods and analytical procedures.	published	No citation expected for Directive 305/2011; Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 351
EN 16907-7	Earthworks - Part 7: Hydraulic placement of extractive waste	E	This European Standard gives general guidelines for the hydraulic placement of extractive wastes applicable, in particular, to the extractive industries. The scope of this European Standard includes any dam, confining embankment or other structure serving to contain, retain, confine or otherwise support such wastes on surface in a terrestrial environment. This standard therefore addresses the characterisation of the extractive waste for the purposes of hydraulic placement in the MWF both as part of the confining embankment and for safe storage, and in addition: - specifies minimum requirements for the data to be acquired before the design and execution stage of a hydraulic fill project; - provides guidelines for the selection of the type of confining embankment appropriate for the selected site; - provides guidelines for the selection and characterisation of the construction materials; - establishes general principles on how to design and execute the hydraulic fill project from pre deposition through operation to closure and rehabilitation; - provides guidelines for monitoring and quality control of all stages of the hydraulic fill project to ensure long-term safety and stability.	published		CEN/TC 396
EN ISO 12006-3:2022	Building construction - Organization of information about construction works - Part 3: Framework for object-oriented information (ISO 12006-3:2022)	E, I	This document specifies a language-independent information model which can be used for the development of dictionaries used to store or provide information about construction works. The model is extended by instantiating content, such as further objects and their relationships, allowing the content to serve as an ontology, taxonomy, meronymy, lexicon and thesaurus. NOTE 1 Lexicons are resources for comprising lexical entries for a given language NOTE 2 Meronymies are	published		CEN/TC 442

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			type of hierarchies which deals with part-whole relationships NOTE 3 Ontologies are formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualization. It enables classification systems, information models, object models, data templates and process models to be cross-referenced from within a common framework. This document provides the description of an API allowing the interconnection of data dictionaries as described in ISO 23386.			
EN ISO 16739-1:2020	Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) for data sharing in the construction and facility management industries - Part 1: Data schema (ISO 16739-1:2018)	E, I	The Industry Foundation Classes, IFC, are an open international standard for Building Information Model (BIM) data that are exchanged and shared among software applications used by the various participants in the construction or facility management industry sector. The standard includes definitions that cover data required for buildings over their life cycle. This release, and upcoming releases, extend the scope to include data definitions for infrastructure assets over their life cycle as well. The Industry Foundation Classes specify a data schema and an exchange file format structure. The data schema is defined in - EXPRESS data specification language, defined in ISO 10303-11, - XML Schema definition language (XSD), defined in XML Schema W3C Recommendation, whereas the EXPRESS schema definition is the source and the XML schema definition is generated from the EXPRESS schema according to the mapping rules defined in ISO 10303-28. The exchange file formats for exchanging and sharing data according to the conceptual schema are - Clear text encoding of the exchange structure, defined in ISO 10303-21, - Extensible Markup Language (XML), defined in XML W3C Recommendation. Alternative exchange file formats may be used if they conform to the data schemas. ISO 16739-1:2017 of IFC consists of the data schemas, represented as an EXPRESS schema and an XML schema, and reference data, represented as definitions of property and quantity names, and formal and informative descriptions. A subset of the data schema and referenced data is referred to as a Model View Definition (MVD). A particular MVD is defined to support one or many recognized workflows in the construction and facility management industry sector. Each workflow identifies data exchange requirements for software applications. Conforming software applications need to identify the model view definition they conform to.	published		CEN/TC 442
EN ISO 23386:2020	Building information modelling and other digital processes used in construction - Methodology to describe, author and	E, I	This document establishes the rules for defining properties used in construction and a methodology for authoring and maintaining them, for a confident and seamless digital share among stakeholders following a BIM process. Regarding the definition of properties and groups of properties, this document provides: — definitions of properties and groups of	published		CEN/TC 442

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	maintain properties in interconnected data dictionaries (ISO 23386:2020)		properties as a list of attributes; — definitions of all the provided attributes. Regarding the authoring and maintaining process, this document provides: — definitions and roles of applicants; — definitions and roles of experts and the commission of experts; — definitions of request's attributes; — definitions of expert's attributes; — requirements to establish the management rules to interconnect data dictionaries through the mapping process for properties and groups of properties. To apply the methodology of this document, it is presupposed that the following are in place: — an established governance model for a data dictionary; — a framework for a network of data dictionaries. It is not in the scope of this document to provide the content of the interconnected data dictionaries.			
EN ISO 23387:2020	Building information modelling (BIM) - Data templates for construction objects used in the life cycle of built assets - Concepts and principles (ISO 23387:2020)	E, I	This document sets out the principles and structure for data templates for construction objects. It is developed to support digital processes using machine-readable formats using a standard data structure to exchange information about any type of construction object, e.g. product, system, assembly, space, building etc., used in the inception, brief, design, production, operation and demolition of facilities. This document provides the specification of a taxonomy model that defines concepts from ISO 12006-3:2007, i.e. objects, collections and relationships between them, to support the information need for the specific purpose of the data template. This document provides an EXPRESS specification with extensions of the EXPRESS-G notation and specification from ISO 12006-3:2007. These extensions have been provided to support market needs developed since the publication of ISO 12006-3 in 2007. This document provides the rules for linking between data templates and IFC classes within a data dictionary based on ISO 12006-3:2007. This document provides the rules for linking between data templates and classification systems within a data dictionary based on ISO 12006-3:2007. The target audience of this document is software developers and not construction industry domain experts appointed to create data templates based on sources describing information needs. It is not in the scope of this document to provide the content of any data templates. The data structure provided is intended to be used for developing specific data templates based on standards developed in ISO/IEC, CEN/CENELEC, national standardization organizations, or other sources describing information needs.	published		CEN/TC 442
EN ISO 19650-4	Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil	E, I	ISO 19650 part 4 provides detailed process and criteria for the decision points in the process of executing an information exchange within information management as defined by ISO 19650. It promotes a sustainable approach to information	published		CEN/TC 442

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	engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) - Information management using building information modelling - Part 4: Information exchange (ISO/FDIS 19650-4:2022)		exchange where the immediate delivery of information does not preclude its future use. It is applicable to any information exchange within project stages (ISO 19650 part 2) and within in-use events (ISO 19650 part 3). All development and information exchanges should be executed under the appropriate security controls (ISO 19650 part 5). It supports the satisfaction of a specific EIR/AIR related to an individual information exchange of any type of information by enumerating criteria relating to completeness, compliance to formal exchange schemas, the continuity of concepts between exchanges and the elimination of spatial and specification conflicts			
prCEN/TR (WI=00442031)	Framework and Implementation of Common Data Environment Solutions, in accordance with EN ISO 19650	E	This New Work Item will extend the basic information given in the EN ISO19650 and in the "Guidance to EN ISO 19650". It will detail and structure the concept of a Common Data Environment (CDE) as a workflow for the collaborative process of managing the information and information containers as solutions that fit to the management and project processes inherent for BIM It may be necessary to introduce further concept details as elements for understanding and implementation. Archiving and versioning of information containers can become very complex when considering various typical information situations of a project. Further elements, rules and terminology for information management and digitisation may need to be explained and technically framed in the context of a CDE. It will be a large advantage developing at the same time the "Open API for CDE" in TC442 WG2 In particular this Work Item will describe - how to link a CDE according to EN ISO 19650 to an already existing Asset Management Systems of the Asset Owner. - how to maintain and manage "living documents" like Information Models (AIM, PIM) - how to maintain, exchange and manage Information Requirements like (OIR, AIR, EIR) as well as BIM Execution Plans (BEP) - how to use and implement Information Delivery Plans for the above entities (MIDP and TIDP in ISO 19650) - how to manage and collaborate between various Information Containers like models, requirements, container states - how to support Process Workflow by a CDE based on the IDM concept It will simply have to describe how to provide "Common Data Environment" throughout the whole life cycle (horizontal aspect) and throughout the spectrum of management levels and stakeholders (vertical aspect). In the work item proposed here, all important terms, processes and targets are to be expanded around the CDE concept. Relations to already existing normatives will be given. Informative attachments such as templates and examples could be	under drafting		CEN/TC 442

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			provided to the benefit of planner, supplier and operator as further guidelines.			
<u>prEN 17549-1</u>	Building information modelling - Information structure based on EN ISO 16739 1 to exchange data templates and data sheets for construction objects - Part 1: Data templates and configured construction objects	E	<p>The digital transformation of the construction industry includes also the digital transformation of the supply change of construction products. With ISO 16739-1 exists an open language to design, transfer and maintain construction models. The construction models (eg. of a building) contain a digital twin of real-life products. The data of these products should be transported in a digital format on the way from the manufacturer to the building owner. This product data should be expressed also in an easy and open way. The creators of product data files should be able to do this manually or automatically, as they like it. The users of product data should be able to use it to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Import products easily in the as-planned-bim-models to plan with the products in an early stage of development • Import delivered real life products easily in their as-built-bim-models to document them for a later stage of development <p>These scenarios fit in the business models of manufacturers, planners, construction companies and facility managers. The working group 4 of CEN-TC442 has published proposals for creating new work items in the sector of CEN regarding the storage and the transport of product data in the sector of building information modelling (BIM): prEN ISO 23386: Building information modelling and other digital processes used in Construction – Methodology to describe, author and maintain properties in interconnected dictionaries prEN ISO 23387: Data templates for construction works entities, Part 1: Objects, collections, and relationships defining the general structure of data templates This standard defines a format for exchanging empty product data templates and filled product data templates (product data) and therefore fills the missing link between the product data sources (e.g. catalogues) from the manufacturers to the construction models of the designers and owners. The part 1 of the standard describes a way to represent information templates and configured products in a library based on a structure based on ISO 16739-1 (prEN ISO 16739-1) and how this relates to the upcoming standards prEN ISO 23386 and prEN ISO 23387. The part 2 will define the way, how a (requirements) request can be formulated with EN ISO 16739 and how this can be used to represent variants of configurable products. The requests by part 2 will be applicable to product libraries based on part 1. The part 2 will furthermore define a way, to create a constraint based product library for highly configurable products to support an interactive selection process. The application of an request to a "Part1-Library" and to a "Part2-Library" shall response same products as the result. It is up to</p>	under approval		<u>CEN/TC 442</u>

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			the manufacturers to choose the way, they want to represent their products ("Part1-Library" and/or "Part2-Library"), they just have to be sure, that all requests can be applied to both types of libraries.			
prEN 17549-2	Building information modelling - Information structure based on EN ISO 16739 1 to exchange data templates and data sheets for construction objects - Part 2: Configurable construction objects and requirements	E	The digital transformation of the construction industry includes also the digital transformation of the supply chain of construction products. With EN ISO 16739-1 exists an open language to design, transfer and maintain construction models. The construction models (e.g. of a building) contain a digital twin of real-life products. The data of these products should be transported in a digital format on the way from the factory to the building owner. This product data should be expressed also in an easy and open way. The creators of product data files should be able to do this manually or automatically, as they like it. The users of product data should be able to use it to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Express their requirements related to products Describe configurable products Import product data easily in the BIM models at any stage of the project (design, construction, operation) Export product data easily from the BIM models at any stage of the project (design, construction, operation) These scenarios fit in the business models of manufacturers, planners, construction companies and facility managers. The working group 4 of CEN-TC442 has published proposals for creating new work items in the sector of CEN regarding the storage and the transport of product data in the sector of building information modelling (BIM): EN ISO 16739-1:2018: Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) for data sharing in the construction and facility management industries- Part 1: Data schema EN ISO 12006-3: Building construction – Organization of information about construction works – Part 3: Framework for object-oriented information prEN ISO 23386: Building information modelling and other digital processes used in Construction – Methodology to describe, author and maintain properties in interconnected dictionaries prEN ISO 23387: Data templates for construction works entities, Part 1: Objects, collections, and relationships defining the general structure of data templates This standard defines a format to negotiate product data templates, express requirements and describe configurable products and therefore fills the missing link between the product data sources (e.g. catalogs) from the manufacturers and the BIM models of the designers, builders, and owners.	under approval		CEN/TC 442
prEN ISO 19650-6	ISO 19650-6: Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil	E, I	This Document outlines the concepts and principles to ensure that Health and Safety information is developed, shared and managed collaboratively, ensuring the economic, environmental and social benefits are secured. This Document; 1) specifies requirements for the collaborative	under drafting		CEN/TC442

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	engineering works, including building information modelling -- Information management using building information modelling – Part 6: Health and Safety		sharing of structured H&S information throughout the asset life-cycle. 2) supports the progressive development of structured H&S information for all built assets. 3) provides guidance on how H&S information is produced, flows and can be used throughout the asset lifecycle. Whilst all H&S risk information can be included within an information model, this document requires the contextualization and filtering of hazards and risks to prioritize the elevated risks and aspects that are safety critical. 4) sets out a framework (risk information cycle) for the application of H&S information-use through BIM processes and applications. This document specifies how to use H&S information in order to: a) provide a safer and healthier environment for end-users; b) mitigate the inherent hazards and risks across the asset lifecycle; c) result in improved H&S performance, fewer incidents and associated impacts; d) provide for clearer, more assured and relevant H&S information to the 'right-people' at the 'right time'; e) reduce costs across the whole lifecycle of the asset. The exchange and use of H&S information is intended to support: 1) representation of the nature and characteristics of the project, site, built asset and associated activities; 2) representation of H&S hazards, risks and associated factors; 3) the generalization, dissemination and re-use of H&S knowledge and experience. This document is applicable to individuals and organizations that contribute to and influence the definition of design, construction, use (including maintenance) and end of life of a built asset. This standard is intended to address information management at a stage of maturity described as "building information modelling" (BIM according to the ISO 19650 series. However, the principles and requirements of this document can be applied equally to non-BIM projects.			
prEN ISO 22014	Library objects for architecture, engineering, and construction	E, I	Recommendations for defining format and content for construction library objects to support project briefing, design, tendering, construction, and management of built assets. It is intended for all professionals and service providers using generic and product specific data, supporting then development of information throughout the process. To develop an International Standard giving principles and definitions for the symbolic and simplified visual presentation of objects in connection with Building Information Modelling (BIM), and their organization into libraries.	under drafting		CEN/TC442
prEN ISO 23387 rev	Building information modelling (BIM) - Data templates for construction objects used in the life cycle of	E, I	This document sets out the principles and structure for data templates for construction objects. It is developed to support digital processes using machine-readable formats using a standard data structure to exchange information about any type of construction object, e.g. product, system, assembly, space, building etc., used in the inception, brief, design,	under drafting		CEN/TC442

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	built assets - Concepts and principles		production, operation and demolition of facilities. This document provides the specification of a taxonomy model that defines concepts from ISO 12006-3:2007, i.e. objects, collections and relationships between them, to support the information need for the specific purpose of the data template. This document provides an EXPRESS specification with extensions of the EXPRESS-G notation and specification from ISO 12006-3:2007. These extensions have been provided to support market needs developed since the publication of ISO 12006-3 in 2007. This document provides the rules for linking between data templates and IFC classes within a data dictionary based on ISO 12006-3:2007. This document provides the rules for linking between data templates and classification systems within a data dictionary based on ISO 12006-3:2007. The target audience of this document is software developers and not construction industry domain experts appointed to create data templates based on sources describing information needs. It is not in the scope of this document to provide the content of any data templates. The data structure provided is intended to be used for developing specific data templates based on standards developed in ISO/IEC, CEN/CENELEC, national standardization organizations, or other sources describing information needs.			
prEN XXXX (WI=00442035)	Building information modelling (BIM) – Data templates for construction objects used in the life cycle of built assets – Data templates based on European standards and technical specifications	E	This document provides a methodology to create data templates for construction objects that are based on European standards and technical specifications. It provides a process and detailed specification allowing domain experts to implement the content in domain standards for construction objects in a machine readable and interpretable format, by means of property definitions and template definitions on the basis of data dictionaries	under approval	-	CEN/TC 442
EN 17412:2020	Building Information Modelling - Level of Information Need - Part 1: Concepts and principles	E	This document specifies concepts and principles to establish a methodology for specifying level of information need and information deliveries in a consistent way when using building information modelling (BIM). This document specifies the characteristics of different levels used for defining the detail and extent of information required to be exchanged and delivered throughout the life cycle of built assets. It gives guidelines for principles required to specify information needs. The concepts and principles in this document can be applied for a general information exchange and whilst in progress, for a generally agreed way of information exchange between parties in a collaborative work process, as well as for an appointment with specified information delivery. The level of information need provides methods for describing	published		CEN/TC 442

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			information to be exchanged according to exchange information requirements. The exchange information requirements specify the wanted information exchange. The result of this process is an information delivery. This document is applicable to the whole life cycle of any built asset, including strategic planning, initial design, engineering, development, documentation and construction, day-to-day operation, maintenance, refurbishment, repair and end-of-life.			
prEN 17516 (WI=00444181)	Waste - Characterization of granular solids with potential for use as construction material - Compliance leaching test - Up-flow percolation test	E	(1) This document specifies an up-flow percolation test (PT) which is applicable to determine the leaching behaviour of inorganic and non-volatile organic substances from granular solids with potential for use as construction material. The test is not suitable for substances that are volatile under ambient conditions. The granular solids are subjected to percolation with water as a function of liquid to solid ratio under specified percolation conditions. The method is a once-through column leaching test. NOTE 1 Volatile organic substances include the low molecular weight substances in mixtures such as mineral oil. (2) This up-flow percolation test is performed under specified test conditions for granular solids with potential for use as construction material and does not necessarily produce results that mimic specific intended use conditions. This test method produces eluates, which can subsequently be characterized by physical, chemical and ecotoxicological methods according to existing standard methods. The results of eluate analysis are presented as a function of the liquid/solid ratio. The test results enable the distinction between different leaching behaviour. NOTE 2 It is not always possible to adjust test conditions simultaneously for inorganic and organic substances. Test conditions can also vary between different groups of organic substances. Test conditions for organic substances are generally more stringent than those for inorganic substances. The test conditions are generally described in a way that they fit testing organic substances and are also applicable to inorganic substances depending on the set-up. NOTE 3 For ecotoxicity testing, eluates representing the release of both inorganic and organic substances are needed. In this document, ecotoxicological testing is meant to include also genotoxicological testing. NOTE 4 Granular solid waste materials with a low hydraulic conductivity that can cause detrimental pressure build-up are not supposed to be subjected to this test. NOTE 5 This procedure is generally not applicable to solids that are easily biologically degradable and solids reacting with the leachant, leading to, for example, excessive gas emission or excessive heat release, impermeable hydraulically bound solids or solids that swell in contact with water. Granular solid waste materials without potential for	under approval	Mandate: M/366	CEN/TC 444

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			beneficial use are excluded from the scope. NOTE 6 Granular solid waste materials without potential for beneficial use can be materials with gas generation or biodegradation during a potential reuse scenario. This test is applicable to types of granular solid waste of which the general long-term leaching behaviour is known based on previous investigations. (3) In this document the same test conditions as for FprEN 16637-3 (CEN/TC 351/WG 1) are applied in order to allow full comparability of testing construction products and waste derived construction products to avoid double testing. The FprEN 16637-3 test results are eligible in the context of testing granular solids with potential for use as construction material as well. NOTE 7 If a leaching test according to FprEN 16637-3 has been performed, additional prEN 17516 testing does not need to be carried out.			
EN ISO 14008:2019	Monetary valuation of environmental impacts and related environmental aspects	E, I	This document specifies a methodological framework for the monetary valuation of environmental impacts and related environmental aspects. Environmental impacts include impacts on human health, and on the built and natural environment. Environmental aspects include releases and the use of natural resources. The monetary valuation methods in this document can also be used to better understand organizations' dependencies on the environment. During the planning of the monetary valuation, the intended use of the results is considered but the use itself is outside the scope of this document. In this document, monetary valuation is a way of expressing value in a common unit, for use in comparisons and trade-offs between different environmental issues and between environmental and other issues. The monetary value to be determined includes some or all values reflected in the concept of total economic value. An anthropocentric perspective is taken, which asserts that natural environment has value in so far as it gives utility (well-being) to humans. The monetary values referred to in this document are economic values applied in trade-offs between alternative resource allocations, and not absolute values. This document does not include costing or accounting, although some valuation methods have the term "cost" in their name. This document does not include the development of models linking environmental aspects to environmental impacts.	published		CEN/SS S26
EN ISO 14007:2019	Environmental management — Guidelines for determining environmental costs and benefits	E, I	This document gives guidelines for organizations on determining the environmental costs and benefits associated with their environmental aspects. It addresses the dependencies of an organization on the environment, for example, natural resources, and the context in which the organization operates or is located. Environmental costs and benefits can be expressed quantitatively, in both non-	published		CEN/SS S26

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			monetary and monetary terms, or qualitatively. This document also provides guidance for organizations when disclosing related information. This document takes an anthropocentric perspective, i.e. looking at changes that affect human wellbeing (utility) including their concern for, and dependence on, nature and ecosystem services. This includes use and non-use values as reflected in the concept of total economic value when environmental costs and benefits are determined in monetary terms. The ways in which the environmental costs and benefits are used after they have been determined are outside the scope of this document. This document is applicable to any organization regardless of size, type and nature.			
EN ISO 14006:2020	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for incorporating ecodesign	I	This document gives guidelines for assisting organizations in establishing, documenting, implementing, maintaining and continually improving their management of ecodesign as part of an environmental management system (EMS). This document is intended to be used by organizations that have implemented an EMS in accordance with ISO 14001, but it can also help in integrating ecodesign using other management systems. The guidelines are applicable to any organization regardless of its type, size or product(s) provided. This document is applicable to product-related environmental aspects and activities that an organization can control and those it can influence. This document does not establish specific environmental performance criteria.	published		CEN/SS S26
EN ISO 14005:2019	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for a flexible approach to phased implementation	I	This document gives guidelines for a phased approach to establish, implement, maintain and improve an environmental management system (EMS) that organizations, including small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), can adopt to enhance their environmental performance. The phased approach provides flexibility that allows organizations to develop their EMS at their own pace, over a number of phases, according to their own circumstances. Each phase consists of six consecutive stages. The system's maturity at the end of each phase can be characterized using the five-level maturity matrix provided in Annex A. This document is applicable to any organization regardless of their current environmental performance, the nature of the activities undertaken or the locations at which they occur. The phased approach enables an organization to develop a system that ultimately satisfies the requirements of ISO 14001. The guidance does not cover those elements of specific systems that go beyond ISO 14001 and it is not intended to provide interpretations of the requirements of ISO 14001.	published		CEN/SS S26
EN ISO 14004:2016	Environmental management systems	I	ISO 14004:2016 provides guidance for an organization on the establishment, implementation, maintenance and	published		CEN/SS S26

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	— General guidelines on implementation		improvement of a robust, credible and reliable environmental management system. The guidance provided is intended for an organization seeking to manage its environmental responsibilities in a systematic manner that contributes to the environmental pillar of sustainability. This International Standard helps an organization achieve the intended outcomes of its environmental management system, which provides value for the environment, the organization itself and interested parties. Consistent with the organization's environmental policy, the intended outcomes of an environmental management system include: enhancement of environmental performance; fulfilment of compliance obligations; achievement of environmental objectives. The guidance in this International Standard can help an organization to enhance its environmental performance, and enables the elements of the environmental management system to be integrated into its core business process. NOTE - While the environmental management system is not intended to manage occupational health and safety issues, these can be included when an organization seeks to implement an integrated environmental and occupational health and safety management system. ISO 14004:2016 is applicable to any organization, regardless of size, type and nature, and applies to the environmental aspects of its activities, products and services that the organization determines it can either control or influence, considering a life cycle perspective. The guidance in this International Standard can be used in whole or in part to systematically improve environmental management. It serves to provide additional explanation of the concepts and requirements. While the guidance in this International Standard is consistent with the ISO 14001 environmental management system model, it is not intended to provide interpretations of the requirements of ISO 14001.			
EN ISO 14002-1:2019	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for using ISO 14001 to address environmental aspects and conditions within an environmental topic area — Part 1: General	I	This document gives general guidelines for organizations seeking to systematically manage environmental aspects or respond to the effects of changing environmental conditions within one or more environmental topic areas, based on ISO 14001. This document also constitutes a framework for common elements of subsequent parts of the ISO 14002 series.	published		CEN/SS S26
EN ISO 14001:2015	Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use	E, I	ISO 14001:2015 specifies the requirements for an environmental management system that an organization can use to enhance its environmental performance. ISO 14001:2015 is intended for use by an organization seeking to manage its environmental responsibilities in a systematic manner that	published		CEN/SS S26

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			contributes to the environmental pillar of sustainability. ISO 14001:2015 helps an organization achieve the intended outcomes of its environmental management system, which provide value for the environment, the organization itself and interested parties. Consistent with the organization's environmental policy, the intended outcomes of an environmental management system include: enhancement of environmental performance; fulfilment of compliance obligations; achievement of environmental objectives. ISO 14001:2015 is applicable to any organization, regardless of size, type and nature, and applies to the environmental aspects of its activities, products and services that the organization determines it can either control or influence considering a life cycle perspective. ISO 14001:2015 does not state specific environmental performance criteria. ISO 14001:2015 can be used in whole or in part to systematically improve environmental management. Claims of conformity to ISO 14001:2015, however, are not acceptable unless all its requirements are incorporated into an organization's environmental management system and fulfilled without exclusion.			
EN ISO 14040:2006	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework (ISO 14040:2006)	E, I	ISO 14040:2006 describes the principles and framework for life cycle assessment (LCA) including: definition of the goal and scope of the LCA, the life cycle inventory analysis (LCI) phase, the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) phase, the life cycle interpretation phase, reporting and critical review of the LCA, limitations of the LCA, the relationship between the LCA phases, and conditions for use of value choices and optional elements. ISO 14040:2006 covers life cycle assessment (LCA) studies and life cycle inventory (LCI) studies. It does not describe the LCA technique in detail, nor does it specify methodologies for the individual phases of the LCA. The intended application of LCA or LCI results is considered during definition of the goal and scope, but the application itself is outside the scope of this International Standard.	published		CEN/SS S26
EN ISO 14040:2006/A1:2020	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework - Amendment 1 (ISO 14040:2006/Amd 1:2020)	E, I		published		CEN/SS S26
EN ISO 14044:2006	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and	E, I	ISO 14044:2006 specifies requirements and provides guidelines for life cycle assessment (LCA) including: definition of the goal and scope of the LCA, the life cycle inventory analysis (LCI) phase, the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)	published		CEN/SS S26

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	guidelines (ISO 14044:2006)		phase, the life cycle interpretation phase, reporting and critical review of the LCA, limitations of the LCA, relationship between the LCA phases, and conditions for use of value choices and optional elements. ISO 14044:2006 covers life cycle assessment (LCA) studies and life cycle inventory (LCI) studies.			
EN ISO 14044:2006/A1:2018	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines - Amendment 1 (ISO 14044:2006/Amd 1:2017)	E, I		published		CEN/SS S26
EN ISO 14044:2006/A2:2020	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines - Amendment 2 (ISO 14044:2006/Amd 2:2020)	E, I		published		CEN/SS S26
EN ISO 14045:2012	Environmental management - Eco-efficiency assessment of product systems - Principles, requirements and guidelines (ISO 14045:2012)	E, I	ISO 14045:2012 describes the principles, requirements and guidelines for eco-efficiency assessment for product systems including: the goal and scope definition of the eco-efficiency assessment; the environmental assessment; the product-system-value assessment; the quantification of eco-efficiency; interpretation (including quality assurance); reporting; critical review of the eco-efficiency assessment. Requirements, recommendations and guidelines for specific choices of categories of environmental impact and values are not included. The intended application of the eco-efficiency assessment is considered during the goal and scope definition phase, but the actual use of the results is outside the scope of ISO 14045:2012.	published		CEN/SS S26
EN ISO 14046:2016	Environmental management - Water footprint - Principles, requirements and guidelines (ISO 14046:2014)	E, I	ISO 14046:2014 specifies principles, requirements and guidelines related to water footprint assessment of products, processes and organizations based on life cycle assessment (LCA). ISO 14046:2014 provides principles, requirements and guidelines for conducting and reporting a water footprint assessment as a stand-alone assessment, or as part of a more comprehensive environmental assessment. Only air and soil emissions that impact water quality are included in the assessment, and not all air and soil emissions are included. The result of a water footprint assessment is a single value or a profile of impact indicator results. Whereas reporting is within the scope of ISO 14046:2014, communication of water footprint results, for example in the form of labels or declarations, is outside the scope of ISO 14046:2014.	published		CEN/SS S26

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ISO 15686-1:2011	Buildings and constructed assets — Service life planning — Part 1: General principles and framework	I	ISO 15686-1:2011 identifies and establishes general principles for service life planning and a systematic framework for undertaking service life planning of a planned building or construction work throughout its life cycle (or remaining life cycle for existing buildings or construction works). The life cycle incorporates initiation, project definition, design, construction, commissioning, operation, maintenance, refurbishment, replacement, deconstruction and ultimate disposal, recycling or re-use of the asset (or parts thereof), including its components, systems and building services. ISO 15686-1:2011 is applicable to the service life planning of individual buildings.	published		ISO/TC 59/SC 14
ISO 15686-3:2002	Buildings and constructed assets — Service life planning — Part 3: Performance audits and reviews	I	ISO 15686-3:2002 is concerned with ensuring the effective implementation of service life planning. It describes the approach and procedures to be applied to pre-briefing, briefing, design, construction and, where required, the life care management and disposal of buildings and constructed assets to provide a reasonable assurance that measures necessary to achieve a satisfactory performance over time will be implemented. The cost implications of service life planning and the broader issues of sustainability (e.g. embodied energy, land use) are not developed in ISO 15686-3:2002.	published		ISO/TC 59/SC 14
ISO 15686-10:2010	Buildings and constructed assets — Service life planning — Part 10: When to assess functional performance	I	ISO 15686-10:2010 establishes when to specify or verify functional performance requirements during the service life of buildings and building-related facilities, and when to check the capability of buildings and facilities to meet identified requirements. ISO 15686-10:2010 is applicable to any scope of holdings, whether a set (or portfolio) of buildings, a single building (large or small) or a facility which is part of a building (such as one group of spaces, one floor or several floors). It is applicable to the range of roles from the owners and managers to the occupants, tenants, or other users or stakeholders.	published		ISO/TC 59/SC 14
ISO/TR 15686-11:2014	Buildings and constructed assets — Service life planning — Part 11: Terminology	I	ISO/TR 15686-11:2014 provides a compilation of the terms and definitions of concepts that have been standardized to establish a vocabulary applicable to the aspects of both the construction and use of a building or civil engineering works and the service life planning of the same, as applied in the documents of ISO/TC 59/SC 14 Design life. ISO/TR 15686-11:2014 consists of terms and definitions included in the different parts of ISO 15686, along with their abbreviated designations, where applicable. The terms and definitions of concepts listed in Clause 3, along with any relevant abbreviated designations, include those representing concepts that have been standardized and/or applied within SC 14, as well as a number of others that have originally been developed elsewhere within the ISO technical structure. A cross reference is	published		ISO/TC 59/SC 14

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			included in each of the definitions to the specific part of ISO 15686 in which the concept is defined, as well as to the International Standard (s) from where the definition originates, unless otherwise noted.			
ISO/TS 12720:2014	Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works — Guidelines on the application of the general principles in ISO 15392	I	ISO/TS 12720:2014 provides guidance for the application of the general principles of sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works elaborated in ISO 15392. It shows the different actors involved with the construction works how to take these principles into account in their decision-making processes in order to increase the contribution of the construction works to sustainability and sustainable development. ISO/TS 12720:2014 provides a step-by-step approach for: encouraging the application of the general principles by all stakeholders at each stage of the project and its use, from the decision to build and the initial development of the project brief until the end-of-life of the construction works; helping interested parties to consider and/or incorporate sustainability thinking in all phases of the building's or civil engineering works' life cycle, for all relevant issues of concern, by raising key questions in relation to the general principles; understanding the outcome (effect) of the application of the general principles; and building on acquired experience to develop best practices and engendering a continuous improvement process.	published		ISO/TC 59/SC 17
ISO/AWI TS 12720	Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works — Guidelines on the application of the general principles in ISO 15392	I		under development		ISO/TC 59/SC 17
ISO 15392:2019	Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works — General principles	I	This document identifies and establishes general principles for the contribution of buildings, civil engineering works and other types of construction works (hereinafter referred to collectively as construction works) to sustainable development. It is based on the concept of sustainable development as it applies to the life cycle of construction works, from inception to the end-of-life. This document is applicable to new and existing construction works, individually and collectively, as well as to the materials, products, services and processes related to their life cycle. This document does not provide performance levels (benchmarks) that can serve as the basis for sustainability claims. *NOTE 1 The principles established in this document are intended to be applied broadly in the context of construction works. Specific applications are the subject of other related documents. *NOTE 2 Construction works are designed to meet numerous	published		ISO/TC 59/SC 17

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			requirements, such as those expressed and established by authorities having jurisdiction. In some circumstances, it can be necessary to go beyond established requirements to contribute further to sustainable development. *NOTE 3 In this document, unless explicitly stated, the term 'product(s)' implies construction product (3.7) and the term 'service(s)' implies construction service (3.8). This document is not intended to provide the basis for assessment of organizations or other stakeholders, but does acknowledge the importance of their role in the context of contributions to sustainable development by buildings, civil engineering works and other construction works. *NOTE 4 More detailed discussions on social responsibility aspects, relative to organizations, can be found in ISO 26000.			
ISO 20887:2020	Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works — Design for disassembly and adaptability — Principles, requirements and guidance	I	This document provides an overview of design for disassembly and adaptability (DfD/A) principles and potential strategies for integrating these principles into the design process. This document provides information for owners, architects, engineers, and product designers and manufacturers to assist in their understanding of potential DfD/A options and considerations, and for other parties who are responsible for financing, regulating, constructing, transforming, deconstructing, or demolishing construction works. This document is applicable to all types of buildings (e.g. commercial, industrial, institutional, and residential), civil engineering works (e.g., dams, bridges, roads, railways, runways, utilities, pipelines) and their constituent parts. It can be used for new construction, refurbishment and renovation, and in the design of incremental improvements in, or complete redesign of, buildings, building systems, civil engineering works, and their constituent parts. This document also provides guidance on measuring performance regarding each DfD/A principle and related objectives. This document is intended to be used in conjunction with and following the principles set out in ISO 15392 and the ISO 15686 series. This document does not set specific levels of performance for the disassembly or adaptability of constructed works, however, it does include requirements that are mandatory for the implementation of specific DfD/A principles that are applicable when these principles are adopted.	published		ISO/TC 59/SC 17
ISO 21929-1:2011	Sustainability in building construction — Sustainability indicators — Part 1: Framework for the development of indicators and a core	I	ISO 21929-1:2011 establishes a core set of indicators to take into account in the use and development of sustainability indicators for assessing the sustainability performance of new or existing buildings, related to their design, construction, operation, maintenance, refurbishment and end of life. Together, the core set of indicators provides measures to express the contribution of a building(s) to sustainability and	published		ISO/TC 59/SC 17

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	set of indicators for buildings		sustainable development. These indicators represent aspects of buildings that impact on areas of protection related to sustainability and sustainable development. The object of consideration in ISO 21929-1:2011 is a building or a group of buildings and the external works within the site (curtilage). ISO 21929-1:2011 follows the principles set out in ISO 15392 and, where appropriate, is intended for use in conjunction with, and following the principles set out in, ISO 26000, ISO 14040 and the family of International Standards that includes ISO 14020, ISO 14021, ISO 14024 and ISO 14025. Where deviation occurs or where more specific requirements are stated, ISO 21929-1:2011 takes precedence. ISO 21929-1:2011 adapts general sustainability principles for buildings; includes a framework for developing sustainability indicators for use in the assessment of economic, environmental and social impacts of buildings; determines the aspects for consideration when defining a core set of sustainability indicators for buildings; establishes a core set of indicators; describes how to use sustainability indicators; and gives rules for establishing a system of indicators. ISO 21929-1:2011 does not give guidelines for the weighting of indicators or the aggregation of assessment results.			
ISO/TS 21929-2:2015	Sustainability in building construction — Sustainability indicators — Part 2: Framework for the development of indicators for civil engineering works	I	ISO/TS 21929-2:2015 establishes a list of aspects and impacts which should be taken as the basis for the development of sustainability indicators for assessing the sustainability performance of new or existing civil engineering works, related to their design, construction, operation, maintenance, refurbishment and end-of-life. Together, the indicators developed from this list of aspects and impacts provide measures to express the contribution of a civil engineering works to sustainability and sustainable development. The developed indicators should represent aspects of civil engineering works that impact on issues of concern related to sustainability and sustainable development. The object of consideration in ISO/TS 21929-2:2015 is a civil engineering works, a part of the civil engineering works or a combination of several civil engineering works.	published		ISO/TC 59/SC 17
ISO 21930:2017	Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works — Core rules for environmental product declarations of construction products and services	I	ISO 21930:2017 provides the principles, specifications and requirements to develop an environmental product declaration (EPD) for construction products and services, construction elements and integrated technical systems used in any type of construction works. ISO 21930:2017 complements ISO 14025 by providing specific requirements for the EPD of construction products and services. ISO 21930:2017 establishes a core set of requirements to be considered as core product category rules (PCR) to develop an EPD for any construction product or service. In addition, this	published		ISO/TC 59/SC 17

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			<p>document, as the core PCR document for construction products, construction elements and integrated technical systems: a) includes the rules for calculating the life cycle inventory analysis (LCI), the predetermined environmental indicators and the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) results that are reported in the EPD; b) describes which life cycle stages are considered in a particular type of EPD, which processes are to be included in the life cycle stages and how the stages are subdivided into information modules; c) defines rules for the development of scenarios; d) includes the rules for reporting relevant environmental and technical information that are not covered by LCA; e) defines the core elements to be included in an EPD; f) establishes the structure of a project report; g) defines the conditions under which construction products can be compared, based on the information provided by an EPD; h) provides requirements and guidelines on PCR for sub-categories of construction products; i) includes mandatory and unalterable requirements for any PCR based on this document. - - EPDs for construction products, as described in this document, are primarily intended for use in B2B communication, but their use in B2C communication under certain conditions is not precluded. For EPDs intended for B2C communication, refer to ISO 14025 (see 5.4). The assessment of social and economic impacts at the product level is not covered by this document. NOTE 1: In this document, unless otherwise designated, the term construction product is used for any good(s) or service(s) related to construction works. - - NOTE 2: Construction assemblies, construction elements and integrated technical systems, incorporated within construction works, can be considered construction products.</p>			
ISO 21931-1:2022	Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works — Framework for methods of assessment of the environmental, social and economic performance of construction works as a basis for sustainability assessment — Part 1: Buildings	I	<p>This document provides a general framework for improving the quality and comparability of methods for assessing the environmental, social and economic performance of construction works, and their combination as a basis for the sustainability assessment of buildings. It identifies and describes issues to be taken into account in the development and use of methods of assessment of the environmental, social and economic characteristics, aspects and impacts of new or existing buildings. These relate to the building's design, production of construction products, materials and components, construction, operation, maintenance and refurbishment and end-of-life processes. This document is applicable to the assessment of the building (or part thereof) and the external works within its site (curtilage). - - NOTE: The assessment of environmental, social and economic aspects related to the location of the building, such as those resulting</p>	published		ISO/TC 59/SC 17

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			from transportation of the users, can extend beyond the area of the building site. This document does not set benchmarks or levels of performance relative to environmental, social and economic impacts and aspects.			
ISO 14053:2021	Environmental management — Material flow cost accounting — Guidance for phased implementation in organizations	I	This document gives practical guidelines for the phased implementation of material flow cost accounting (MFCA) that organizations, including small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), can adopt to enhance their environmental performance and material efficiency. The phased approach provides flexibility that allows organizations to develop their MFCA activities at their own pace, according to their own circumstances. The resulting information can act as a motivator for organizations to seek opportunities to simultaneously generate financial and environmental benefits by reducing material losses and energy consumption. This document is applicable to any organization, regardless of its level of development, the nature of its activities, or the location at which these activities occur. This document provides basic calculation procedures to analyse saving potentials by avoiding material losses. Detailed calculation procedures or information on techniques for improving material or energy efficiency are out of the scope of this document.	published		ISO/TC 207/SC 1
ISO 14009:2020	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for incorporating material circulation in design and development	I	This document gives guidelines for assisting organizations in establishing, documenting, implementing, maintaining and continually improving material circulation in their design and development in a systematic manner, using an environmental management system (EMS) framework. These guidelines are intended to be used by those organizations that implement an EMS in accordance with ISO 14001. The guidelines can also help in integrating material circulation strategies in design and development when using other management systems. The guidelines can be applied to any organization regardless of its size or activity. This document provides guidelines for design strategies on material circulation to achieve the material efficiency objectives of an organization, by focusing on the following aspects: type and quantity of materials in products, product lifetime extension, recovery of products, parts and materials. In design and development, many aspects are considered, such as safety, energy efficiency, performance and cost. Although important, they are not addressed in this document.	published		ISO/TC 207/SC 1
ISO/TS 14029:2022	Environmental statements and programmes for products — Mutual recognition of environmental product	I	This document specifies requirements for mutual recognition arrangements (MRAs) and gives guidance on how to initiate developments on MRAs between environmental product declaration (EPD) and footprint communication programme operators. It addresses administrative and operational duties, through evaluation of such programmes, and how to	published		ISO/TC 207/SC 3

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	declarations (EPDs) and footprint communication programmes		externally communicate the results of the cooperation as well as plans for future related activities. This document is primarily applicable to MRAs but can also be a basis for bilateral agreements.			
ISO/DIS 14020	Environmental statements and programmes for products - Principles and general requirements	I	This document establishes principles and specifies general requirements that are applicable to all types of product-related environmental statements and environmental statement programmes. Environmental statements result from environmental statement programmes and include self-declared environmental claims, ecolabels, environmental product declarations (EPDs) and footprint communications. This document is intended to be used in conjunction with other standards in the ISO 14020 family.	published		ISO/TC 207/SC 3
ISO/AWI 59014	Secondary materials — Principles, sustainability and traceability requirements	I		under development		ISO/TC 207/SC 5
ISO/AWI 14075	Principles and framework for social life cycle assessment	I		under development		ISO/TC 207/SC 5
ISO/DTS 14074	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles, requirements and guidelines for normalization, weighting and interpretation	I	This document specifies principles, requirements and guidelines for normalization, weighting and life cycle interpretation, in addition to those given in ISO 14040 and ISO 14044. The document is applicable to any life cycle assessment (LCA) and footprint quantification study. In particular, this document addresses: the use of normalization and its limitations; the use of weighting and its limitations; the selection or development of weighting factors; the generation of single scores; requirements that relate to documentation and reporting. For the interpretation phase, it provides, in addition to ISO 14044, procedures and guidance for: performing completeness, sensitivity and consistency checks; addressing uncertainties and limitations; documenting conclusions and recommendations. This document does not specify the composition of panels for weighting nor does it specify multi-criteria decision analysis. This document does not intend to recommend or require a specific weighting approach or method or any priority of one weighting approach or method over another as they are based on value choices. Organizations have the flexibility to implement LCA in accordance with the intended application and the requirements of the organization.	published		ISO/TC 207/SC 5
ISO/AWI TR 4083	Wood and wood-based products - Overview related to the concepts	I		under development		ISO/TC 287

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	of renewability, reusability, recoverability, recyclability, compostability, biodegradability and circularity – Terminology and existing methodology					
<u>ÖNORM B 4710-1</u>	Beton - Festlegung, Eigenschaften, Herstellung, Verwendung und Konformität - Teil 1: Regeln zur Umsetzung der ÖNORM EN 206 für Normal- und Schwerbeton	N	Die vorliegende ÖNORM gilt für Normal- und Schwerbeton, der für Ortbetontragwerke, für vorgefertigten Bauteilen sowie für Fertigteile für Gebäude und Ingenieurbauwerke verwendet wird. Der Beton kann als Baustellenbeton, als Transportbeton oder in einem Werk für Betonfertigteile hergestellt werden.	published		Austrian Standards International (A.S.I.) - Committee 010
<u>ÖNORM B 3140</u>	Rezyklierte Gesteinskörnungen für ungebundene und hydraulisch gebundene Anwendungen sowie für Beton	N	Diese ÖNORM legt auf Grund der speziellen geografischen, topografischen und klimatischen Verhältnisse, die in Österreich herrschen, den Prüfparameterumfang für rezyklierte Gesteinskörnungen für die Herstellung von ungebundenen und hydraulisch gebundenen Gemischen für den Ingenieur- und Straßenbau gemäß ÖNORM EN 12620 und Gesteinskörnungen für Beton gemäß ÖNORM EN 12620 fest.	published		Austrian Standards International (A.S.I.) - Committee 051
<u>ÖNORM B 3141</u>	Herstellung von Recycling-Baustoffen aus Aushubmaterialien (überwiegend natürliche Gesteinskörnungen) / engl. Production of recycled building materials from excavated materials (mainly natural aggregates)	N	This ÖNORM summarises the construction and environmental requirements for recycled building materials from excavated materials. It covers excavated materials that are processed into natural aggregates or mixtures of natural aggregates with recycled aggregates and are described in the Austrian Federal Waste Management Plan. The environmental requirements are specified in the Austrian Federal Waste Management Plan. The technical requirements for construction are taken from the European product standards and their national implementation documents and they are categorised. Furthermore, this ÖNORM defines unique material designations for the manufactured recycled building materials. Aggregate mixtures can be produced by adding recycled aggregates (in minor quantities) for technical improvement to the above-mentioned recycled building materials. Mixtures already present in situ are also covered by this ÖNORM. Recycled building materials covered by the Austrian Recycling	under development		Austrian Standards International (A.S.I.) - Committee 051

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			Building Materials Ordinance are dealt with in ÖNORM B 3140 and are therefore not part of this ÖNORM.			
<u>ÖNORM B 3151</u>	Rückbau von Bauwerken als Standardabbruchmethode	N	The present ÖNORM describes the measures needed for the planning and execution of the dismantling of buildings and specifies separation principles for the different materials in regard to recovery or disposal. The dismantling objective is to obtain mono-material mostly free of harmful substances and impurities. If ecologically appropriate, technically possible and not unreasonably cost-intensive, the waste products of the dismantling process shall be recovered. Harmful substances and impurities have to be examined and separated to obtain recyclable mono-fraction demolition materials. The present ÖNORM describes the dismantling in structural and civil engineering including line construction works and paved area.	published		<u>Austrian Standards International (A.S.I.) - Committee 157</u>
<u>ÖNORM S 2126</u>	Grundlegende Charakterisierung von Aushubmaterial vor Beginn der Aushub- oder Abräumtätigkeit	N	This Standard applies to basic characterization of dredged material prior to excavation or removal, which occurs after excavation or removal as waste and which is to be fed for recycling or disposal.	published		<u>Austrian Standards International (A.S.I.) - Committee 157</u>
<u>DIN 18007:2022-09</u>	Demolition works - Concepts, procedures, fields of application	N		published		DIN
<u>DIN 18007:2022-09</u>	Concrete Recycling - Quality assurance in high voltage electric pulse disaggregation of waste concrete	N		published		DIN
<u>BS 6187:2011</u>	Code of practice for full and partial demolition	N		published		BSI - British Standards
<u>ASTM E3073-17</u>	Standard Guide for Development of Waste Management Plan for Construction, Deconstruction, or Demolition Projects	N	<p>1.1 The purpose of this guide is to facilitate development of a waste management plan for construction, deconstruction, or demolition projects (hereafter, construction waste management (CWM) plan).</p> <p>1.2 This guide applies to CWM plans developed for construction, renovation, deconstruction, and demolition of buildings, factories, parking structures, and any other structure, as well as above- and below-ground infrastructure.</p> <p>1.3 This guide includes CWM plan guidance for the wastes generated on-site during construction, deconstruction, and demolition projects.</p> <p>NOTE 1: For example, included is any waste generated during these activities such as structural and finish materials and construction chemicals; construction product and materials packaging; construction office waste, including paper</p>	published		ASTM International

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			<p>documents; wastes from site development work, such as excavated soils, rocks, vegetation, and stumps; and other ancillary items, such as broken tools, safety materials/personal protective equipment, and food and beverages and their packaging. The list of items above is offered for illustration purposes only; it is not intended to be fully inclusive of all materials from a construction, deconstruction, or demolition project that are suitable for reuse, repurposing, manufacturer reclamation, composting, and recycling.</p> <p>1.4 Waste generated in the manufacture, preparation, or fabrication of materials before delivery to the job site are not in the scope of this guide.</p> <p>1.5 This guide does not change or substitute for any federal, state, or local statutory or regulatory provisions or requirements related to the handling, control, containment, transport, or disposition of any particular material.</p> <p>1.6 This standard does not purport to address all of the safety concerns, if any, associated with its use. It is the responsibility of the user of this standard to establish appropriate safety, health, and environmental practices and determine the applicability of regulatory limitations prior to use.</p> <p>1.7 This international standard was developed in accordance with internationally recognized principles on standardization established in the Decision on Principles for the Development of International Standards, Guides and Recommendations issued by the World Trade Organization Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) Committee.</p>			
ASTM C 1881-20	Standard Guide for Closed-Loop Recycling of Scrap Gypsum Panel Products	N	<p>1.1 This guide provides guidance for the handling, physical condition and compositional considerations for selecting scrap gypsum panel products and the recycled gypsum derived from that scrap for recycling into new gypsum panel products. 1.2 This guide applies to material derived from gypsum panel products manufactured in accordance with Specifications C1177/C1177M , C1178/C1178M , C1278/C1278M , C1396/C1396M , and C1658/C1658M . 1.3 This guide does not dictate the minimum amount of recycled gypsum a gypsum panel product manufacturer is required for use in producing new gypsum panel products. 1.4 This guide does not address recycling of gypsum panel products from demolition or renovation projects. Note 1: While these sources are outside the scope, they are not precluded from being recycled. This guide may be used as a basis for determination of basic criteria for any stream, as agreed upon between the</p>	published		ASTM International

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			contractor, recycler, and the gypsum panel product manufacturer. 1.5 This guide does not address the suitability of recycled gypsum for other uses such as an agricultural amendment, for use in gypsum-based joint compounds or gypsum plaster, as an admixture or other uses of gypsum aside from gypsum panel products. 1.6 The values stated in inch-pound units are to be regarded as standard. The values given in parentheses are mathematical conversions to SI units that are provided for information only and are not considered standard. 1.7 This standard does not purport to address all of the safety concerns, if any, associated with its use. It is the responsibility of the user of this standard to establish appropriate safety, health, and environmental practices and determine the applicability of regulatory limitations prior to use. 1.8 This international standard was developed in accordance with internationally recognized principles on standardization established in the Decision on Principles for the Development of International Standards, Guides and Recommendations issued by the World Trade Organization Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) Committee.			
SN 509430:1993 SIA 430	Entsorgung von Bauabfällen bei Neubau-, Umbau- und Abbrucharbeiten	N	Die vorliegende Empfehlung gilt für Neubau- Umbau- und Abbruchvorhaben im Hoch und Tiefbau. Sie beschreibt die bei der Projektierung und Ausführung notwendigen Massnahmen für einen umweltgerechten Umgang mit Bauabfällen und legt die Grundsätze für die Trennung der einzelnen Materialgruppen und -fraktionen im Hinblick auf die Verwertung, Behandlung oder Ablagerung der Bauabfälle fest.	publishe d		SNV - Schweizer Normenvereinigung
SN 509493:1997 SIA 430	Deklaration ökologischer Merkmale von Bauprodukten	N	Diese Norm gilt für die Deklaration ökologisch relevanter Merkmale von Bauprodukten mit dem Deklarationsraster SIA 493.01 bis 493.14.	publishe d		SNV - Schweizer Normenvereinigung
SN 562162:1994 SIA 430	Recyclingbeton	N	Die vorliegende Empfehlung behandelt die anwendungsgerechte Verwertung von Teilen des Bauschuttes.	publishe d		SNV - Schweizer Normenvereinigung
NEN 5884:2008 nl	Waste and waste disposal - Terms and definitions for waste from building and demolition processes	N	This standard contains a list of terms and definitions concerning waste from building and demolition processes.	publishe d		NEN - Niederlandse Norm
DWA-M 303:2012-04	Wiedernutzbarmachung von kleinen Grundstücken - Abbruch, Rückbau und geordnete Entsorgung	O	inen wichtigen Baustein zur Befriedigung der Nachfrage nach innerstädtischem Wohnraum stellt die Wiedernutzung von bereits bebauten, aber nicht mehr genutzten Flächen dar. Daher rückt die Wiedernutzung kleinerer bebauter Grundstücke in das Bewusstsein der Stadtplanung und der Bauherren. Das Merkblatt richtet sich gezielt an die meist privaten Besitzer von nicht mehr nutzbaren Bauten, die eine Nachnutzung anstreben. Der Schwerpunkt liegt hierbei auf	publishe d		

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			dem Gebäude und womöglich anzutreffenden Schadstoffen. Fragen des Boden-, Natur- und Gewässerschutzes werden am Rande gestreift und durch Verweise auf die einschlägigen Rechtsbereiche und technischen Normen abgehandelt.			
<u>ISO/CD 59020</u>	Circular economy – Measuring and assessing circularity	I	The document provides a general methodology for defining, implementing, operating, monitoring, reviewing, maintaining and improving circular economy aspects when acquiring or supplying products, and through the usage of a Product Circularity Data Sheet. This general methodology contains a set of requirements that need to be established by an organization aiming to use the concerned data sheet throughout supply chain management processes, including the secure reporting and exchanging of information. The document also provides recommendations for the definition and sharing of a Product Circularity Data Sheet, considering the type, content and format of information to be provided to support the implementation of cost-effective circular business models for products.	under development		ISO/TC 323
<u>ISO/NWP 59040</u>	Circular Economy — Product Circularity Data Sheet	I	The document provides a general methodology for improving the accuracy and completeness of circular economy related information based on the usage of a Product Circularity Data Sheet when acquiring or supplying products. This general methodology contains then a set of requirements that need to be established by an organization aiming to use the concerned data sheet when acquiring or supplying products, which also includes the trusted reporting and exchanging of circular economy related information. The document also provides guidance for the definition and sharing of a Product Circularity Data Sheet, considering the type, content and format of information to be provided. This guidance and these requirements are intended to be applicable to all organizations, regardless of type, size and nature. These requirements implement a qualitative approach for business-to-business data exchange to be inclusive with small and medium businesses/enterprises and to protect confidential information.	under development		ISO/TC 324

Table 5 - Identified Formal Standard Documents

Annex 2:

Document	Title	Type of Standard	Summary or Scope	Status	Consortial Standards, Regulations, Directives, Reference	Standardization Body & Technical Committees & Working Groups (CEN/CENELEC; ISO/IEC, ETSI; IEEE etc)
<u>VDI 2074:2014-07</u>	Recycling in the building services	N	Diese Richtlinie verfolgt einen integrierten Ansatz unter Berücksichtigung des Wertschöpfungsgedankens. Sie gibt für die einzelnen Phasen des Lebenszyklus von Gebäuden und Anlagen Hinweise zur Schaffung von Kreisläufen, indem sie für alle Beteiligten an Planung, Errichtung, Nutzung und Modernisierung oder Rückbau mögliche Beiträge aufzeigt. Die Richtlinie trägt durch die Bevorzugung der stofflichen Verwertung dem Recyclingansatz Rechnung. Durch die Vermeidung von Behandlungs- und Deponiekosten bei regionalen Entsorgern können Kosten eingespart werden.	published		Verein deutscher Ingenieure
<u>VDI 2095 Part 1:2014-07</u>	Emission control - Treatment of mineral construction-site and demolition waste - Stationary and mobile demolition waste recycling facilities	N	This guideline gives instructions for the emission control of facilities for crushing and grading of mineral construction-site and demolition waste in mobile or stationary recycling facilities. An in-depth consideration of aspects of noise protection and occupational safety is not the concern of this guideline.	published		Verein deutscher Ingenieure

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<p><u>VDI 2095 Part 2:2014-07</u></p>	<p>Emission control - Storage, handling, treatment of mixed construction-site and demolition waste, bulky waste, and commercial waste</p>	<p>N</p>	<p>This standard provides guidance material on emission reduction for equipment used in the treatment of mixed construction and demolition wastes according to the Commercial Waste Ordinance, and for equipment in which such wastes are treated alongside industrial waste and bulky waste. In this standard, the above categories of equipment are all described by the unitary term "equipment for treatment of construction and demolition wastes". This standard also applies to plants</p>	<p>published</p>		<p>Verein deutscher Ingenieure</p>
<p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/958161/de</p>	<p>ASHVIN</p>		<p>ASHVIN aims at enabling the European construction industry to significantly improve its productivity, while reducing cost and ensuring absolutely safe work conditions, by providing a proposal for a European wide digital twin standard, an open source digital twin platform integrating IoT and image technologies, and a set of tools and demonstrated procedures to apply the platform and the standard proven to guarantee specified productivity, cost, and safety improvements.</p>	<p>under development (due 23.9.2023)</p>		<p>H2020 project</p>

Table 6 - Non-Formal Identified Standards

